

META-ANALYSIS OF CONTEMPORARY HUMOUR

PRACTICES AND DEMOCRATIC ATTITUDES

DELIAH

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Introduction

This document forms part of the Democratic Literacy and Humour (DELIAH) project, which explores the complex and multifaceted role of humour in various artistic expressions, cultural spaces, and both online and offline public fora. The project investigates how humour can act as a tool either to support or undermine democratic participation and processes across Europe. This particular document examines academic literature on contemporary humour practices and their intersection with democratic practices in six European countries—Belgium, Estonia, Germany, the Netherlands, Slovakia, and Spain—while also drawing on relevant adjacent studies.

The humour and politics research field

The body of research reviewed reflects a growing interest in the relationship between humour and politics, especially from 2013 onwards. Much of this surge in scholarly attention has been prompted by the rise of humour on social media platforms, with a specific focus on harmful and exclusionary forms of online humour. In all six countries studied by the DELIAH project, online humour practices are a significant area of academic investigation, particularly in terms of how they are used to delineate and enforce symbolic boundaries. These boundaries involve negotiations over issues of inclusion, exclusion, and equality. The existing literature predominantly relies on qualitative methodologies, with an emphasis on the content of humour and the actors who produce it. However, there is comparatively little attention paid to the audiences of humorous content.

Humour in boundary work

The role of humour in boundary work is inherently ambiguous. Humour can contribute to the drawing and redrawing of symbolic boundaries through both general communicative mechanisms and those that are more specific to humour itself. Among the general mechanisms are the categorisation of social groups, the selective presentation of information, and the construction of the ‘socially marked’ versus the ‘socially unmarked’. More uniquely, humour can function through the re-appropriation of cultural elements via self-parody, the sharing of group-specific humour practices, the use of ridicule to sanction deviant behaviour, and the strategic use of light-heartedness to diffuse conflict and deliver potentially controversial messages. These uses of humour can work to (re-)shape symbolic boundaries in both inclusive and exclusionary directions.

Humour and the dissemination of political information

Humour is often cited as a potent medium for transmitting political information, owing to its engaging qualities and its ability to facilitate the viral dissemination of messages. Nevertheless, the link between humour and increased political knowledge appears to be largely correlational rather than causal. Evidence suggests that individuals with higher baseline levels of political knowledge are more likely to be drawn to political infotainment, including humorous content, rather than such content itself being responsible for increased political knowledge. However,

humour can perform what researchers call a ‘gateway effect’. This refers, first, to its capacity to draw attention to specific political topics from among the vast array of issues circulating in the public sphere. Second, humour may serve as a point of entry for younger individuals or those with moderate political interest, potentially encouraging deeper engagement over time.

Humour and persuasion

The evidence concerning humour’s persuasive power remains inconclusive. While some studies suggest that humour can contribute to changing attitudes, the broader academic consensus indicates that robust and consistent evidence of humour’s persuasive capacity is still lacking. That said, humour can play a priming role by shaping the issues that are most cognitively accessible to audiences, thereby subtly influencing the opinions expressed and behaviours. Moreover, humour has been implicated in contemporary processes of political radicalisation, although the specific mechanisms through which this occurs remain poorly understood and under-researched.

Humour and the public debate

Although humour can contribute to the deliberative quality of the public debate, most humour practices serve an expressive function. That is to say, they enable the expression of feelings such as anger and frustration, providing emotional relief, and they communicate preferences, but they often fail to provide detailed justifications for them. Other humour practices are primarily driven by the desire to have fun. Accordingly, they focus on anecdotes and do not convey relevant political content. Finally, a significant proportion of the humorous messages that circulate online express exclusionary and antidemocratic attitudes.

Humour for political mobilisation and participation

Humour’s gateway effect has implications for mobilisation and political participation. Particularly individuals with latent views that align with the humorous messages can be encouraged to participate through humour. Mainstream political parties have increasingly incorporated humour into their communication strategies, which is believed to help candidates connect with younger demographics and foster voter engagement. Furthermore, self-deprecating humour allows political candidates to present themselves as relatable and down-to-earth. Meanwhile, authoritarian populists have used online humour as a strategic communication tool, successfully combining biting sarcasm with emotional appeals grounded in anger. Finally, social movements use humour to attract social support, defuse tensions following conflict or repression, and preemptively mitigate hostile responses. More recently, the emergence of ‘connective’ forms of mobilisation—facilitated by digital technologies—has further expanded the role of humour in collective action.

Humour and the implementation of political decisions

One notable gap in the existing literature is the lack of systematic research on how humour is used to enforce political decisions. Although there are multiple examples of public authorities

using humour in communication campaigns to nudge citizen behaviour or promote public policy, these practices have not been thoroughly examined.

Humour and political accountability

In terms of political accountability, the humour employed by citizens and mass media tends to focus on scrutinising the moral integrity and credibility of elected officials. At the same time, humour can serve as a defensive mechanism for politicians. For instance, the use of self-deprecating humour—particularly about minor or trivial matters—can deflect serious scrutiny by shaping how the media frames political narratives, allowing deeper issues to go unexamined.

Social groups' relationship with humour

Methodologically, much of the research in this domain relies on small-N or case-based studies that often overlook how different social groups produce, engage in, or respond to humour. However, there is evidence that the appreciation of humour is correlated with pre-existing beliefs and attitudes. Accordingly, harmful forms of humour—those associated with sexist, racist, ethno-nationalist, or authoritarian views—can be expected to resonate with white individuals who have lower levels of formal education and live in economically declining or socially stagnant, i.e. 'left behind', rural areas. Conversely, individuals who are women, non-heterosexual, university-educated, and/or urban-based are less likely to participate in or appreciate such humour. There is also reason to believe that the way humour is used and received may vary according to whether a group is socially dominant or marginalised. Marginalised groups may be more attuned to the harms of humour directed at them by dominant groups, but they also tend to engage in self-parody as a form of empowerment and resistance. In contrast, dominant groups are often more inclined to dismiss the impact of harmful humour and to engage in humour that mocks others rather than themselves.

Strategies against harmful humour

Currently, there is a scarcity of research on strategies aimed at addressing harmful forms of humour, despite its potentially damaging influence—particularly on younger audiences. Two general approaches to countering harmful humour can be identified. The first consists of targeted interventions in specific settings, such as educational environments. These may include non-judgmental narrative exchanges and the use of counter-humour to challenge antidemocratic or exclusionary attitudes. Additionally, efforts could be made to equip parents with tools to monitor and respond to potentially harmful content encountered by their children online.

The second approach aims to transform the broader cultural repertoire. Rather than directly confronting harmful humour, which can inadvertently amplify its content or provoke backlash, this strategy seeks to offer new narratives through which individuals can articulate their demands in a less toxic manner. Realising such a shift would require collaboration with key actors in the cultural and political spheres who possess the capacity to influence public discourse and media narratives.

1 INTRODUCTION

Democratic Literacy and Humour (DELIAH) examines the multifaceted role of humour in artistic forms, cultural spaces, and online and offline fora, identifying how humour can either support or undermine democratic participation and processes in Europe. To this end, the project carries out research in six countries across Europe; namely, Belgium, Estonia, Germany, the Netherlands, Slovakia, and Spain. This document (D1.2) is part of an initial meta-analysis of contemporary humour practices and democratic attitudes in Europe, which consists of two parts. The first one has resulted in a dataset of relevant studies (D1.1)^[1]. The second one (D1.2) consists of an in-depth discussion of this literature.

More specifically, this review outlines the state of the art, assesses the robustness of its main findings, and, ultimately, theorises how humour works in democracy. In doing so, it locates relevant developments in humour practices and democratic engagement across the six DELIAH countries, and it explores the relationship between different demographic groups and forms of humour that are linked to various ideological positions. These include, but are not limited to, opposition to racial equality, gender equality, and other social inclusion processes; delegitimization of climate-change science; demonisation of migrants; and rejection of democratic, egalitarian, and multicultural values. This information will inform the design of focus groups and survey modules in later stages of the DELIAH project. Finally, the meta-analysis contributes to the identification of potential strategies to confront harmful humour (see Info Box 1).

Despite drawing on a previous dataset of studies (D1.1), this document has been edited to be self-contained, i.e., it can be read without consulting D1.1. This implies that the full references of the studies cited here are provided at the end, so that readers do not need to refer to D1.1. However, this also means that a significant proportion of the studies in the dataset have not been cited. Only the most relevant or representative publications have been included, in order to ensure that the extension of the document remains within reasonable limits.

The meta-analysis discusses and assesses the literature on humour and politics in the DELIAH countries. Thus, the features of this research—e.g., the qualitative nature of most studies—constrain the kind of analysis that is carried out in this review. Where appropriate, studies on adjacent topics or on humour practices elsewhere are also considered, in order to strengthen, qualify or develop some of the arguments.

Finally, given the interdisciplinary nature of DELIAH and of research on humour and politics, info boxes have been added to the document to clarify terms specific to some disciplines or research strands and to provide background information. Info boxes also help to broaden the potential readership of the document, while providing a more fluent reading experience to those who are already familiar with key terms and debates and can thus skip redundant information.

Info Box 1

Harmful humour refers to humour practices that are intended to or which actually contribute to undermining democracy, to promoting an authoritarian regime or actor, to excluding some social groups, or to organising social relations in a non-egalitarian way^[1].

Hate speech is defined by the United Nations as ‘any kind of communication in speech, writing or behaviour, that attacks or uses pejorative or discriminatory language with reference to a person or a group on the basis of who they are, in other words, based on their religion, ethnicity, nationality, race, colour, descent, gender or other identity factor’^[2]. Accordingly, hate speech refers to a broader range of communicative practices than the ‘advocacy of national, racial or religious hatred that constitutes incitement to discrimination, hostility or violence’, which is prohibited under international human rights law^[3].

The document is organised into twelve sections. In the following one an overview of research on humour and politics in the six DELIAH countries is provided. Sections 3 to 10 take stock of how humour works in democratic political systems, while section 11 discusses social groups’ relationship with humour. Section 12 deals with potential strategies against harmful forms of humour.

In order to examine how humour practices are used and with what effects in democratic political systems (sections 3-10), we adopt a modified version of the ‘problem-based approach’ to democratic theory^[4], which offers a comprehensive and flexible analytical framework. This approach inquires into the kinds of ‘problems’ that a political system needs to solve, or the ‘functions’ that it must fulfil, ‘to count as “democratic”’^[4]. Briefly, democratic political systems need, first, to include political actors to enable self-government. Second, they have to ensure that institutional arrangements and prevailing social practices allow political preferences and priorities to be formed, expressed, and contested, resulting in collectively binding decisions. Decisions are collectively binding if they can be enforced, i.e., implemented. Finally, they can be consented to, revised, and traced back to the citizenry if they are part of an accountable decision-making process. Importantly, these ‘functions’ ought to be fulfilled at different levels. For example, to count as ‘democratic’, political systems ought to ensure that *individuals* are able to form their political preferences autonomously (micro level); that they can come together to form *groups* to promote certain ideas more effectively (meso level); and that the *political system* eventually makes political decisions that reflect the distribution of will among the citizenry (macro level).

Drawing on this framework and adapting it to the manifold role of humour in politics, as described by the existing literature, the discussion has been organised as follows: Section 3 introduces the conceptual building blocks needed to comprehend humour in the context of politics, i.e., its nature, dimensions, and main functions, on which subsequent segments will draw. Section 4 explores the use of humour in the (re-)drawing of symbolic boundaries. It thus addresses issues of inclusion and status within the political community, as well as the use of humour to form and maintain other social groups or to challenge existing definitions of social groups. Whether and how humour practices convey relevant political information and persuade people is examined in sections 5 and 6, respectively. Section 7 addresses the use of humour in the context of political mobilisations, while topics pertaining to humour practices and the democratic debate are examined in section 8. Section 9 touches on the use of humour to facilitate the implementation of political decisions. Finally, section 10 examines humour practices in relation to political accountability.

2 HUMOUR AND POLITICS RESEARCH IN THE DELIAH COUNTRIES

D1.1 compiled over 300 studies on the relationship between contemporary humour and politics in Belgium, Estonia, Germany, the Netherlands, Slovakia, and Spain^[1]. The entries refer to humour practices in these countries, which are not necessarily specific to them. Assuming an association between population size and the size of the national economy, on the one hand, and the scholarly production, on the other, two countries, Spain and Estonia, stand out for their high number of contributions to the dataset (146 and 61 studies respectively), and one country, Germany, for its comparatively low number (44 entries). Furthermore, the search for studies on humour and politics in the Netherlands yielded 34 results, which is somewhat lower than expected given that humour is a well-established topic in Dutch academia. This is due to a significant amount of research carried out by Dutch-based academics focusing on cases outside the Netherlands or neglecting the intersection of humour and politics.

In any case, all DELIAH countries conform to a similar pattern regarding the temporal distribution of entries. Overall, the database shows a gradual increase in the number of publications, especially after 2007, and a weaker increase after 2021. However, countries differ as to when research on humour and politics started to intensify. The evolution of both the Estonian and Spanish humour and politics research fields has been relatively steady, with an observable increase after 2013 and a peak around 2021 and 2022. In contrast, the distribution of the studies in Belgium, Germany, and the Netherlands attests to the exponential growth of humour and politics scholarship between 2020-2025. Depending on the country, nearly half of the entries or well over half of them were published in this relatively short period.

This evolution can be partly explained by the passage of time. Namely, research conducted in the early 21st century was more likely to concentrate on humour practices from before the 21st century and thus to fall outside the scope of this literature review, while literature databases like Scopus have increased their coverage since 2000^[5], thus gradually increasing the likelihood of finding relevant studies. Nonetheless, the topical nature of this research suggests that factors related to political and social developments are also at play, as much of the recent research on humour and politics concentrates on social media and, in particular, on harmful forms of online humour.

As a result, online humour practices are a major topic of research in all six DELIAH countries, despite some variation among them due to the strong intermingling of research themes (Table 1). In the German case, in particular, research on far-right humour, which in other countries is often dealt with as part of research on online humour, is emerging as a distinctive thematic strand.

Moreover, the topical distribution of entries shows—again, consistently across countries—that humour is primarily used by social actors to (re-)draw and police symbolic boundaries, i.e., to negotiate issues of inclusion, exclusion and equality (see section 4). In this regard, some variation among countries can be observed. Humour practices in Belgium, Germany, and the Netherlands deal with forms of cultural pluralism linked to relatively recent migration processes, which lack sharp boundaries between ethnic diversity, religious pluralism, immigration, etc. In contrast, humour in Estonia and Slovakia is often associated with well-established, territorially concentrated ethnic groups, including questions pertaining to the definition of the national community vis-à-vis this enduring ethnic diversity and the particular geopolitical position of these countries. Both in Estonia and Slovakia contemporary studies on ethnic humour extend a

longer history of ethnicity-related humour and research on it, while so-called *ethno-comedy* scholarship, which developed in Germany in the early and mid-2000s, can also be regarded as a consolidated research area. In contrast, boundary issues are primarily explored in the Spanish humour and politics research field through studies on gender—a topic that also figures prominently in the Netherlands.

Additional salient research topics are the use of humour for negotiating collective memory and confronting historical trauma, which is salient in Estonia and Slovakia, and the role of humour in *infotainment*, which attracts above-average attention in the Netherlands, Slovakia, and Spain. Furthermore, humour in the context of contentious politics, in particular in social protests, is a relatively popular topic in Spanish scholarship. Finally, Belgian research reflects the demographic realities of this country's multicultural population and debates around social cohesion, and it has documented shifts in patterns of news consumption and the participation of especially young people, their humour practices, and the use of humour in educational contexts.

The research fields in the DELIAH countries and their evolution appear closely linked to broader societal and media developments, notwithstanding some gaps in the literature, to which we will turn below. Beyond thematic changes, additional shifts can be observed. For example, the assessment of humour has recently shifted towards more critical views that see it as democratically harmful. In line with people's preferred humour styles^[6], including in the political arena^[7], humour research has traditionally been, and still is to a significant extent, biased towards a celebratory view of humour as a democracy-strengthening factor. While this bias persists, scholars are increasingly attentive to humour's ambiguous or 'double-edged'^[8] nature vis-à-vis democracy—a position that, interestingly, has long been firmly rooted in the Estonian research field and is gaining traction in the other DELIAH countries.

Moreover, we have treated humour as an object of research and a form of communication that can have political effects, in line with most of the literature reviewed. However, some cutting-edge research—e.g., the NoJoke project, funded by the European Research Council—is moving away from this approach and towards previous *epistemological* perspectives on humour. According to these views, humour provides a lens through which socio-political dissonances can be identified, i.e., a privileged point of access to social reality, rather than being an object within this reality that contributes to shaping it. Whether these epistemological perspectives will gain further traction remains to be seen.

Table 1: Overview of the Humour and Politics Research Fields in the DELIAH Countries

	Belgium	Estonia	Germany	Netherlands	Slovakia	Spain
Main Research Topics	Online humour and digital engagement	Online humour and digital engagement	Online humour and digital engagement	Online humour and digital engagement	Online humour and digital engagement	Online humour and digital engagement
	Cultural and ethnic pluralism	Cultural and ethnic pluralism	Cultural and ethnic pluralism	Cultural and ethnic pluralism	Cultural and ethnic pluralism	Gender issues
	Youth (including education)	Collective memory and historical events	Right wing and populist humour	Infotainment	Infotainment	Infotainment
				Gender issues	Collective memory and historical events	Contentious politics
Main Types of Humour	Memes and online humour	Memes and online humour	Memes and online humour	Memes and online humour	Memes and online humour	Memes and online humour
	Jokes and face-to-face humour	Jokes and face-to-face humour	Jokes and face-to-face humour	Jokes and face-to-face humour	Jokes and face-to-face humour	Humour in printed and written form
	Humour in audio-visual media	Humour in printed and written form	Humour in audio-visual media	Humour in audio-visual media	Humour in audio-visual media	Humour in audio-visual media

If we classify humour practices based on the media in which they occur, the use of memes and other online humour practices consistently attract attention across countries, in line with the topical distribution of research described above. Similarly, humour in audiovisual media has been widely explored, except in Estonia. Nevertheless, it is notable that research sometimes focuses on just one or a few particularly influential shows. This is the case of research in the Netherlands, where a relatively high number of studies focus on *Zondag met Lubach* (*Sunday with Lubach*, presented by Arjen Lubach). In the case of Germany, although many publications focus on humour practices in audiovisual media, few explore satirical news shows specifically, despite their massive growth and presence in public broadcasting since the early 2010s. Jokes and other face-to-face humour practices receive significant attention across all of our countries, except in Spain, while printed and written humour is popular in Estonia, due to the influence of folklore studies, and in Spain, due to the popularity of humorous comic books and graphic novels.

Although research reflects broader societal developments, and differences between countries can be partly explained by these, the influence of the specific scholarly communities engaged in humour and politics research should not be underestimated. In this regard, there is no simple pattern of research dispersion or concentration across specific disciplines that accounts for these differences. In a country like Spain, which has an overproportionate number of studies given its population size, the research landscape is fragmented, attracting the attention of scholars from various disciplines, including communication and media studies, sociology, political science and linguistics. The same applies to Germany, a country with a lower proportionate number of publications given its size. In contrast, research in Estonia, which has produced a comparatively high number of studies, is mainly rooted in folkloristics, ethnology, digital media research, and memory studies, and is concentrated in a few interconnected institutions, particularly the University of Tartu and the Estonian Literary Museum.

While we lack a full-fledged explanation of these differences, the available evidence suggests that any satisfactory account should be based on the principles of equifinality and path-dependency. That is, any explanation will have to assume that different initial conditions (e.g., concentration vs fragmentation of the research field) can lead to similar outcomes (e.g., a disproportionately high number of studies). Similarly, it will have to assume that contingent past events can have major consequences in the present, as illustrated by the cases of Estonia and Slovakia.

In this regard, the first free scholarly publication on jokes, especially political and risqué ones, in the late Soviet Union appeared in Estonia, namely the anthology *Genres of Verbal Texts: Anecdote* (1989). The very fact that such a volume was published marked a significant breakthrough and helped spark a broader wave of interest in humour research across Estonia and post-Soviet countries in general. In this context, the personal interests of particularly prolific and influential scholars turned out to be decisive. A key figure in the Estonian case is Arvo Krikmann, who focused on collecting and classifying Soviet political jokes and shaped the school of humour studies in the Estonian Literary Museum. His students, among them Liisi Laineste and Piret Voolaid, are responsible or co-responsible for about half of the publications on humour and politics in Estonia included in D1.1.

As regards Slovakia, the relatively limited number of publications on humour and politics in this country stands in contrast to the widespread recognition and media visibility of figures and platforms associated with public humour. These include stand-up comedians such as Jano Gordulič, Simona Salátová, and Jakub Gulík, et al.; creators of cartoon political satire such as Martin 'Shooty' Šútovec or Marek 'Danglár' Gertli, et al.; and popular social media communities and

performers, including Zomri, Fero Joke, and Adolf Snehuliak. Additional manifestations of humour's cultural prominence can be seen in events such as Kremnica Gags, forms of political artistic activism that engage in the deconstruction of populist or misogynistic narratives (e.g., RosieArt), as well as in the rhetorical strategies of populist politicians, who often utilise harmful or aggressive humour as a communicative tool. What stands out in the Slovak context, especially when compared to that of the neighbouring Czech Republic, is the lack of a prominent scholar, such as Jan Chovanec in the Czech context (or Arvo Krikmann in the Estonian one), around whom a school of thought on humour research could emerge.

Finally, although research reflects broader societal developments, there also are significant gaps in the literature. First, subtle forms of humour remain understudied. For example, research examining over 7,500 front pages from major Spanish dailies found that approximately 30% of the pictures in these front pages contained humorous elements (see Image 1)^[9]. These somewhat concealed humour practices receive scant attention. Along these lines, research on *political* humour often glosses over the fine-grained details of humorous discourses in favour of their ideological elements. While these details (e.g., in the form of linguistic choices, framing devices, and timing of the jokes) may be subtle and difficult to pin down, they may be responsible for the humorous effects.

Second, the literature is dominated by qualitative approaches, often focusing on a single case. When social actors' humour practices or their reactions to them are analysed, studies frequently rely on small and non-representative samples, which impedes controlling for relevant factors. Furthermore, attention to long-term historical processes is rare and, perhaps more importantly for the study of political humour, research mostly concentrates on the agent or the content of humour, while neglecting how humorous messages are actually interpreted. When attention is paid to those receiving and reacting to humorous messages, virtually no research measures behavioural effects, only reported ones.

Third, fragmentation of the research field has resulted in the lack of a shared theoretical vocabulary. In this regard, taxonomic incommensurability, in particular, prevents the clarification of mixed results, which abound in this field.

Fourth, there is little research focusing specifically on the emotional dimension of humour and its effects.

Finally, socially marginalised voices are often, albeit not systematically, underrepresented in humour research. Nevertheless, the specific perspectives that are neglected vary between countries. In Estonia, for instance, those of Russo-phone communities, recent immigrants, and LGBTQ+ individuals are understudied. Furthermore, gender-based humour practices do not receive the attention one could expect given the degree of public engagement with gender issues. A similar situation applies to Germany, and in Belgium there is a marked underrepresentation of

Image 1

Source: ^[9] / *El País* (Uly Martin)
Picture of the former Spanish Prime Minister Mariano Rajoy, published in the front page of *El País* on 5 May 2016 with the subtitle 'Rajoy discovers virtual reality'.

Wallonia and minority groups beyond those of Turkish and Moroccan backgrounds, to cite but a few examples.

3 FOUNDATIONS TO COMPREHEND HUMOUR IN THE CONTEXT OF POLITICS

Some basic notions are needed to make sense of humour in the context of politics. To this end, this section briefly addresses the nature of humour as a politically relevant phenomenon, its main dimensions, and its functions, i.e., what humour is used for. Such an approach will feed into the following sections, which focus on how humour practices work—in other words, what the mechanisms underlying humour’s political effects are (Info Box 2).

Info Box 2

Mechanisms are ‘recurrent small-scale events that alter relations among stipulated elements of social life in essentially the same ways whenever and wherever they occur’^[10]. That is, mechanisms describe recurrent processes by which one variable (e.g., a humorous message) influences another variable (e.g., people’s political preferences). These causal paths can consist of different kinds of elements, such as cognitive phenomena, social actions, and social conditions.

Humour has been variously defined as an expression of contempt or ‘sudden glory’^[11], a (non-threatening) incongruity^[12], a form of play^[13], a mood^[14], the upshot of a physiological mechanism of energy management^[15], and ‘one of the most complex cultural accomplishments’^[16], among many other things. In this document, we adopt a pragmatic perspective, and instead of approaching humour from the point of view of what it is, define it according to DELIAH’s main goal, namely the examination of humour’s multifaceted role vis-à-vis democratic participation and democratic processes in Europe. Therefore, we conceptualise humour as a specific form of *communication*, along the lines of Niklas Luhmann’s definition of communication as the synthesis of information, utterance, and (mis)understanding^[17]. In this view, communication is anything that carries some information, can be shared, and is indeed received by another social actor, even if she misinterprets or understands only partly the intended meaning. While this does not imply the adoption of a full-fledged system theoretic perspective, this concept of humour draws on the (system theoretic) assumption that communication is the basic building block of society and thus of politics. In other words, politically relevant humour is humour that has been communicated.

As a form of communication, humour often, albeit not always, conveys a nonthreatening incongruity that does not encourage the receiver to adopt a genuine problem-solving attitude^[18]. These two conditions—namely, humour being nonthreatening and dissociated from genuine problem-solving attitudes—are related to another feature: its emotional dimension. Humour is usually, but not invariably^[19], associated with laughter and amusement, mirth^[13,20], contempt^[21], or similar feelings of superiority—or a combination thereof, as in the case of ‘amused contempt’^[22]. Finally, like many other socially relevant concepts, the meaning of humour is subject to the so-called politics of naming, which implies that the boundaries of what constitutes ‘humour’, as opposed to ‘bad taste’, ‘unfunny’, or ‘serious’, can be shifted by influential social actors. Thus, from a formal

perspective, humour is a ‘family resemblance category’^[23], which lacks a clear and stable conceptual core, yet is used to designate forms of communication that are reasonably similar.

As a species of communication, humour practices can influence the democratic process in the same ways as most other forms of human communication; for example, by providing information, focusing on certain aspects while ignoring others, categorising people, and allowing certain types of actors—e.g., members of historically excluded groups—to participate (through humour) in the public conversation. Humour practices, conceived in this way, gain their social meaning from the interaction between the messages explicitly communicated, the speakers, and the contexts of utterance, which implies that what matters from a political point of view is how humorous communicative acts are interpreted and contribute to the broader social context in which they take place, rather than ‘the good intentions of the joke-makers’ (Stuart Hall cited in ^[22]). Furthermore, humour can have unintended consequences, be misunderstood, and so forth—the same as most other forms of communication.

Beyond these ways of exerting political influence, more distinctive uses of humour can be identified. These are captured by standard theories of humour^[24,25] or theories of humour ‘origin’^[8]. Superiority theory focuses on practices of laughing *at* others, which are interpreted as the result of feeling superior in some way to other people, whereas relief theory puts the emphasis on the alleged physiological benefits that result from, and produce, humour. In this respect, it claims that accumulated ‘energy’ is released through laughter. Incongruity theory, in turn, concentrates on the various layers of meaning or frames that often come together in humour practices, which produce laughter by connecting these frames or moving between them in ways that violate the expectations of the listeners. Finally, play theory construes humour as a form of play, and laughter as a play signal. As other species of play, humour is argued to enable the development of important skills, like creativity and tolerance for diversity and ambiguity, or to serve social functions such as the management of conflicts and the creation of social bonds.

Taken together, these theories suggest that humour is usually used, first, to deprecate other people’s behaviours, traits, or messages. Tellingly, even in the absence of any explicit message, mere laughter directed at someone is usually understood as a form of censure (Image 2). Second, humour practices are also deployed to reduce stress. Third, they serve to bring to light real or perceived inconsistencies in social life (Image 3). As argued by Mary Douglas, ‘if there is no joke in the social structure, no other joking can appear’^[26]. Fourth, they are used to engage in practices that, without a play signal, are likely to attract harsh(er) criticism (Image 4); that is, practices that push the boundaries of what can be said or done in a specific social context. Finally, they contribute to creating a playful and to many people engaging environment.

To be sure, these basic functions of humour do not exhaust the meaning of humour practices in the democratic process. Yet they are conceptual building blocks that are recurrently used in more fine-grained analyses of humour vis-à-vis specific democratic functions, to which we now turn.

Image 2

Source: ^[27] / Voxmemes
https://www.instagram.com/p/Brpedo3Ak_v?ig
Meme showing members of the Spanish nationalist, far-right party Vox laughing at a left-wing, pro-independence, Catalan nationalist.

Image 3

Source: ^[28]
Meme taken from the Spanish *manosphere*. It reads:
-False reports are only 0.01% of all reports.
-They practically do not exist. They are a male chauvinist myth. This proves that they are not a structural problem.
-Femicides are less than 0.001% of all women.
-Male chauvinist! Just one is a lot. Misogynist! Women are not a number. But it is structural violence, ignorant.

Image 4

Source: ^[28]
Meme taken from the Spanish *manosphere*. It reads:
Rape is too strong a word. Better call it surprise sex.

4 HUMOUR AND THE DRAWING OF SYMBOLIC BOUNDARIES

According to the literature on humour and politics, humour practices are mostly used to negotiate symbolic and social boundaries, i.e., to deal with questions such as who belongs to a social group, including the political community as a whole; what behaviours and ideas are acceptable among members of a group; and how to interact, if at all, with out-group members (Info Box 3).

Boundaries are ambiguous in the sense that they both include and exclude specific people, behaviours, or ideas^[29]. Similarly, the role of humour's practices in boundary work is ambiguous, for it can be used to pursue different goals, and humour itself, rather than its content or intended use, can be alienating to some people. For example, humour practices can contribute to challenging existing boundaries in order, e.g., to make them more encompassing and porous, but also to police them to ensure that they remain firmly in place. Additionally, humour practices can simply mirror, and perhaps encourage people to reflect upon, already existing boundary issues (images 5 and 6). Finally, humour practices satisfactorily used to enlarge membership and diversity in a group, as in the case of autonomous anti-capitalist groups in Madrid, can also alienate potential members, such as activists coming from 'a communist or Marxist-Leninist tradition', who deem politics too serious an issue for humour.^[30]

Info Box 3

*The terminology to refer to social groups and describe processes of group formation is extremely large and nuanced. Concepts like identity, collective identity, social identity, social category, categorisation, self-identification, commonality, connectedness, and groupness, among others, capture diverse aspects of what binds people together or contributes to them being included in a social group^[31]. Within processes of group formation, the drawing of **boundaries** is a crucial dimension, albeit not the only one. As argued by Charles Tilly,*

‘enforcement of identity stories occurs chiefly at the boundary: Confrontations between Arabs and Jews become sharp and uniform at the frontier between them. But away from the boundary, who is an Arab or who is a Jew (not to mention what accepting one identity or the other entails for everyday behaviour) remains a matter of intense dispute. As a matter of fact, distinction of one side from the other does not require homogeneity on either side. It merely requires enactment of uniformity at the boundary’^[32].

*Scholars often distinguish between **symbolic boundaries** and **social boundaries**. While the former refers to ‘conceptual distinctions made by social actors to categorize objects, people, practices, and even time and space’, the latter designates ‘objectified forms of social differences manifested in unequal access to and unequal distribution of resources (material and nonmaterial) and social opportunities’^[33]. Humour practices usually do symbolic boundary work, i.e., contribute to creating shared structures of meaning where people, practices, and objects are variously grouped together, separated, and defined. These symbolic boundaries can give rise to social ones, or they can reflect already existing social boundaries. This is why we mostly use the expressions ‘symbolic boundary’ or ‘boundaries’ tout court in this document, as it is not always possible to consistently apply the distinction between symbolic and social boundaries in the context of this literature review.*

*Finally, boundaries vary along different dimensions^[34]. They can be drawn in a way that includes more people or fewer; they can be more or less stable; their political significance can differ; and they can be more or less permeable, often enabling friendly interaction across boundaries while also sometimes preventing any contact or stimulating aggressive behaviour. Accordingly, it is possible to distinguish between more or less **exclusionary** or **inclusionary boundaries** (i.e., fewer people, stable, and impermeable vs encompassing, unstable, and porous)^[35]. However, it should be emphasised that the democratic or anti-democratic consequences of a specific boundary depend on considerations that fall outside the scope of this review and extend beyond the boundary’s inclusionary or exclusionary nature.*

Furthermore, ambiguity can stem from features inherent to some humour practices, including their ‘condensed form of meaning’^[16], their interaction with the larger cultural context, and the way boundaries are organised in a specific social context. For example, cartoons often rely on well-known ‘cultural models’ (e.g., the French Revolution, the Roman Empire, bullfighting) to provide cues to readers to facilitate the recognition of (e.g., French, Italian, Spanish) characters and the interpretation of the image^[36]. This phenomenon, which also characterises other humour practices, such as TV sketches^[37], and which some authors deem typical of humour tout court^[16], can easily turn humour into a species of communication that both challenges and reproduces, sometimes unintentionally, existing boundaries and social images. Alternatively, they can result in cultural products with so many layers of meaning that resist interpretation^[38]. Finally, humour’s ambiguity can result from its interaction with the larger cultural context and the complex structure of existing boundaries. Flemish TV comedies, and TV fiction more generally, are a case in point. While the treatment of LGBTQ+ characters in them suggests normality, even some form of distinction, the way ‘distinctive queers’ are depicted and the cultural context in which these cultural products circulate also perpetuate stereotypes about the supposed incommensurability

between common Flemings (rural and backward) and queerness (urban and socio-culturally progressive)^[39].

Image 5

Source: imgflip.com / Virtual725
<https://imgflip.com/i/76zxc>

This meme uses a well-known format to humorously critique Estonia's aspiration to become a Nordic country and the persistent feeling of exclusion from the Scandinavian community.

Image 6

Source: 9gag.com / mgmtbyprkl
<https://9gag.com/gag/aqbYqDY>

The meme illustrates the identity crisis between embracing Nordic modernism (and liberal values) or Baltic history.

The available research identifies several mechanisms through which humour practices contribute to (re-)drawing and policing boundaries. Some of these mechanisms are only tangentially connected to humour as a distinctive form of communication. For example, humour practices—and stand-up comedy in particular—allow members from underrepresented groups to challenge existing stereotypes ‘by making themselves visible’^[40]. Informal ‘body work’ in the case of female comedians is used to question sexist prejudices^[41], while stand-up comedians like Tigran Gevorkjan can also capitalise on their ethnic background to reflect on diasporic identities, accent-based stereotypes, and social integration.

Other mechanisms are more closely connected to the content of humour than to the agent involved in the humour practice. We will first discuss some that are common to many other forms of communication (i.e., are not exclusive to humour). Typically, they involve the categorisation of people, the selective presentation of information, and the organisation of the ‘socially marked’ and the ‘socially unmarked’^[42].

As regards the first mechanism, humour contributes to categorising people and thus placing them into different groups through the use of images, language, or other means (Image 7). More importantly, social relations are not only symbolically organised into different groups, but the relations between groups are defined in specific ways (e.g., as threatening or burdening, as in Image 7), as well as the groups’ attributes. For example, according to research, jokes about Turks and Surinamese in the Netherlands have contributed to associating these social categories with such attributes as dirtiness and laziness, while underscoring their outgroup, i.e., foreign, status^[43], while similarly racist ideas about Chinese people were spread by early humour practices on Dutch and Flemish social media during the COVID19 pandemic^[44]. In contrast, focusing on the alleged inhuman consequences of immigration policies, as the Dutch Stray Insurgent Clown Army (Clolonel) did in November 2006^[45], is an obvious attempt at making boundaries more

permeable, which relies on the implicit categorisation of migrants as human beings. Interestingly, humorous attacks on specific groups can sometimes contribute to categorising and excluding groups who are not the primary targets of the jokes. This is the case of people with dementia, who are indirectly stigmatised by the dementia jokes used to discredit politicians^[46].

Image 7

Source: Wikipedia / Johan Deckmyn
https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Deckmyn_v_Vandersteen
Cover of a calendar by the Flemish nationalist political party *Vlaams Belang* using a modified image of the comic *The Wild Benefactor* (by Willy Vandersteen). The calendar depicts the mayor of Ghent distributing public money to people of colour and religious minorities. In the bottom right corner of the image, two white Flemings appear frightened or concerned.

Closely linked to this, the selective use of information is another common way of (re-)drawing boundaries. For example, the full constellation of characters targeted by humour practices can greatly determine their overall meaning, as argued vis-à-vis popular Spanish television comedies^[47]. Although contemporary Francoists have become the object of ridicule in them—of a mild type, however—the introduction of ‘failed antagonists’, i.e., left-wing characters who are also parodied, contributes to downplaying the attributes of the former, i.e., their racism, homophobia, authoritarianism, and misogyny, which appear as mere flaws among the many that other characters also displayed. Another interesting example comes from humour practices among Russian-speaking communities in Estonia, which reinforce existing boundaries by avoiding engagement with Estonia-specific political and cultural issues^[48,49]. If lack of engagement prevents the creation of symbolic bridges across boundaries, humour practices depicting global events^[36,50] and leaders^[51] illustrate the opposite phenomenon, namely the redrawing

of national boundaries in a more inclusionary way, reflecting the emergence of world politics^[52] and global society^[53].

However, the significance of processes of categorisation and the selective use of information can only be adequately assessed in connection to a third mechanism, namely the organisation of the socially marked and unmarked through humorous communication. While the socially marked refers to what is considered the special case in social life (e.g., women), the socially unmarked designates the taken-for-granted or generic position (e.g., men)^[42]. Drawing on the previous example of global issues and international leaders, research on Spanish cartoons^[36,51] shows that the incorporation of these topics into humour practices notwithstanding—hence, despite the timid redrawing of symbolic boundaries in a post-national direction—humour practices also contribute to maintaining national boundaries by linking global events to domestic politics, i.e., by keeping the national frame as the normal and default viewpoint from which to assess what is special, namely global or international politics.

Additional ways of (re-)drawing boundaries are related to more distinctive aspects of humour. For example, self-parody underlies practices of re-appropriation of cultural elements—e.g., in the form of the targets of racist jokes telling these jokes—which are not uncommon among marginalised groups. In particular, ‘female’ humour^[54,55] and some humour practices of people with minority ethnic and religious identities^[56–58] have been interpreted in this way, although there is

no shortage of examples of re-appropriation by members of dominant groups (Image 8)^[59–61]. It is important to note that these practices ‘can come in significantly different forms’^[62], despite being treated here under one heading, and that research, although scarce, on the *private* humour practices of members of marginalised groups casts doubt on the extent to which re-appropriation challenges, or rather reproduces (e.g., by reproducing gender-related clichés), existing boundaries and exclusionary content^[63]. In any case, studies focusing on more visible re-appropriation practices by comedians and writers tend to emphasise that re-appropriation is a way of, first, carving out a position of enunciation in which one can be accepted and heard. This enables, subsequently, the gradual revision of prejudices^[54]. Re-appropriation allegedly provides a sense of agency and self-assertion to discriminated people, thus creating bonds of solidarity among group members^[55]. However, the empirical evidence is weak on this point. Regarding members of dominant groups, re-appropriation is used to bring to light attitudes that people would prefer to keep private, and thus to shame those holding them^[64,65].

Image 8

Source: Tujurikkuja / Youtube / Etibar Hasanov

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-FNKJGBtmM8>

Screenshots from the TV show *Tujurikkuja*'s parody of the patriotic song ‘Ei ole ükski ükski maa’ (None of the countries is alone) (2015).

This parody included verses like: ‘Nature knows, fatherland knows, a n**** belongs to Africa. Far away over there, we can tolerate them and all the other animals as well’; ‘Once russophobia in Virumaa goes hand in hand with homophobia, only then can I proudly say that this is my country’; and ‘Nature knows, fatherland knows, we can’t tolerate other Estonians’.

Sharing certain humour practices, and sometimes engaging in *any* humour practice at all, or allegedly failing to do so, is also sometimes used as a boundary-drawing device. Along these lines, progressive politicians in Flanders have been (wrongly) accused of lacking any sense of humour^[66], and similar claims are still made against left-wing social scientists studying humour^[67]. However, often it is the sharing of *specific* humour practices that serves to draw boundaries. ‘Bonding over bashing’ has been observed in far-right alternative media, where mockery of LGBTQ+ topics and ‘woke ideology’ are used to bind participants together^[68]. Similarly, trolling behaviour is used in the *manosphere* to distinguish insiders from outsiders, to discipline participants, and to exclude supposedly emotional and feminine people who cannot endure trolling^[69].

Specific humour practices have also been used as public symbols to emphasise the distinctive nature of political groups, in particular social movements^[30]. Finally, research outside the DELIAH countries has also analysed how consuming specific humour practices is used as a marker of distinction, i.e., to signal various levels of cultural capital^[19].

Beyond the use of humour as a tool with which to signal a specific attribute, or to identify, exclude, or discipline those who lack a certain quality, including the mastery of a specific (e.g., misogynist) cultural code, it has been speculated that sharing humour practices can contribute to binding people together in a ritual-like fashion. According to Marjolein 't Hart, 'laughing together has similar bonding powers like marching, dancing, or singing together'^[70]. Similarly, Raúl Pérez draws on literature from various disciplines to argue that humour 'is a kind of social glue', for certain 'affective reward networks and mechanisms facilitate human social bonding and affiliation because they make us feel good when sharing a laugh in the company of others'^[22]. However, whether these bonding mechanisms work beyond face-to-face interaction is, to our knowledge, an open question.

When alluding to the capacity of shared humour practices to exclude and discipline people, the aforementioned discussion already hints at mockery and ridicule as ways of controlling deviation and policing boundaries. As argued in the previous section, this is a basic function of humour, which is routinely deployed in the drawing and policing of boundaries, even by inclusionary social movements^[30,71] and major dailies^[72]. However, it is its use among far-right groups and networks of online users that has received special attention recently, confirming the use of online humour practices, particularly in the form of memes and social media posts, to ridicule political opponents^[73]. In many cases, 'humiliation, simple mockery, insult and ridicule prevail'^[74], in contradistinction to more sophisticated forms of humour—so much so that online humour practices have become deeply intertwined with hate speech tout court^[74,75]. Admittedly, social media users are often capable of identifying hate speech even when disguised as humour, which they usually dislike^[76], and it has been shown that disparaging humour can backfire and result in the exclusion of the agent, rather than the target of humour^[77]. But it is also the case that hate speech disguised as humour is often seen as less hostile than non-humorous hate speech^[76].

The latter is linked with the use of humour as a form of play, which, in turn, opens the door to humour being used in multiple ways in the (re-)drawing of boundaries. Self-deprecating humour, for example, is frequently employed to present a self-image that is purportedly more authentic and relatable^[72,78]. Similarly, social actors, be they individuals^[78] or collective actors^[71], capitalise on humour's playful, allegedly non-serious nature to tone down and manage social conflicts, thus continuing a larger history of conflict management through humour by social movements^[79]. Furthermore, cartoons have been recently deployed to facilitate dialogue and create less confrontational spaces where to deal with sensitive topics such as radicalisation^[80]. Humour's playful nature is also used to push boundaries and make them more inclusive by adding new voices to the public debate^[81,82], while it is employed by social movements and civic organisations to boost creativity and create engaging environments^[30,71,83].

These uses of humour notwithstanding, social actors have also been shown to draw on humour's playful character to push boundaries in a more exclusionary direction; for example, by pushing the limits of what is deemed acceptable, in order to (re-)legitimise forms of aggression (Image 4)^[28]—an interpretation which, incidentally, resonates with the views of a number of European courts^[84,85]. More generally, the strategy of 'mainstreaming' radical or until recently discredited

ideas, i.e., of making them acceptable to people beyond the primary group of supporters of far-right groups, draws on humour's playful recombination of cultural elements, from references to pop culture to more recent elements taken from video games and contemporary subcultures like that of hipsters^[86].

Finally, research on the contextual constraints of humour practices in the context of boundary work remains underdeveloped. We have limited knowledge about the conditions that encourage social actors to adopt certain strategies over others, and even less information about the conditions that make some strategies more likely to be successful, let alone how to effectively counter-act them^[87]. In line with studies outside the DELIAH countries^[88], research suggests that humour practices in mainstream media, particularly on television, face greater constraints than those happening in smaller, less influential settings (e.g., stand-up comedy clubs)^[89], with social media and online fora probably offering the greatest amount of freedom due to the lack of gatekeepers and the possibility of participating anonymously^[90].

5 HUMOUR AND THE COMMUNICATION OF POLITICAL INFORMATION

Although humour has been argued to be an effective tool to convey political information, due to its engaging nature and concomitant capacity to encourage the viral spreading of messages, research shows a more nuanced picture. For example, people like to share amusing content, and humour is often a predictor of what goes viral, with the additional benefit that shared content usually comes with the endorsement of trusted people, such as a friends or relatives^[91]. This notwithstanding, aggressive humour has been claimed to decrease, rather than extend, the reach of messages^[75].

In the case of infotainment programmes—for example, in the form of satirical shows and late-night TV comedies (see Info Box 4)—, they have been shown to convey relevant informative content, sometimes comprising up to 75% of a show's time^[92–94]. Furthermore, this is sometimes reflected in changes in the meta-journalistic discourse. In the case of *Zondag met Lubach*, for example, the meta-journalistic discourse evolved from conceiving the show as external to the journalistic field to seeing it as a legitimate quasi-insider, to which a specific journalistic role was attributed^[95]. Similarly, research has also emphasised infotainment's potential to successfully convey information on technical issues like the Transatlantic Trade and Investment Partnership^[96], in line with previous studies outside Europe^[97], while online platforms disseminating humorous content, such as *Zomri* in Slovakia, have been identified as 'influencers' vis-à-vis defence topics^[98].

To what extent these are exceptions, or they reflect the informative value of humorous shows and platforms remains an open question. On the one hand, humorous messages are associated with source liking, even in counter-attitudinal contexts, and they are claimed to be capable of attracting and maintaining audience attention^[99], which gives them a strong a priori communication capacity. On the other one, controversies persist over whether humour distorts the information conveyed—for instance, by undermining the seriousness or relevance of issues like climate change^[100]—or whether it can disseminate information accurately^[96].

Info Box 4

*Comedy and satire are ambiguous concepts. **Comedy**, for example, is sometimes used as a synonym for humour, while it can also designate a type of narrative plot. By extension, it can also refer to specific literary works and audiovisual programmes characterised by this narrative plot or by the use of humour tout court. The term **satire** has also expanded its meaning in the recent past^[101]. One still-influential understanding of satire sees it as a genre focused on promoting moral norms. However, more recent scholarship emphasises ‘satire’s ambiguous status as genre, mode, and practice’ as well as the variety of satirical works, which defy definition^[102]. Satire is frequently described as being about specific people or situations that are real, while it also uses techniques like caricature that push it beyond realism. Similarly, satire contains playful elements, but it also draws on negative emotions and is critical, often being ‘orientated towards ends and concerns beyond amusement’^[101]. Additional distinctions are sometimes used (for example, between Horatian and Juvenalian satire^[103]) but not consistently across studies.*

Similarly, even if the association between infotainment consumption and political knowledge is accepted, it remains unclear whether this is due to the capacity of humorous communication to convey information, or if people with above-average political knowledge are simply attracted to political TV shows, including humorous ones. In this regard, a previous review of the literature concluded that people who consume political infotainment are also more likely to consume other sources of political news^[104]. Although research on this is scarce in Europe, some empirical support for this claim can also be found in the DELIAH countries^[105]. Furthermore, the claim is in line with what we know about political interest, which is strongly associated with political knowledge and the consumption of political information^[106]. In this respect, it has been firmly established that political interest is a dispositional type of interest, which means that it is stable—in contradistinction to being activated by contextual stimuli—and it motivates people to *search for* political content. In short, rather than humorous programmes attracting audience attention because they are humorous and capitalising on this to disseminate political information, it is politically well-informed people who consume humorous programmes primarily because they are about politics.

In view of this, scholars have contended that humour might be associated with a more modest ‘gateway effect’^[91,104,107]. According to it, humour’s effects, particularly those of infotainment programmes, are to be found at the margins, as it were. Infotainment, as any other form of public speech for that matter, can contribute to drawing audience attention to specific topics among the plethora of political themes that are continually in circulation. Second, by creating a funny, i.e., engaging environment (see section 3), it can contribute to attracting (usually young) people with some political interest, but not (yet) a strong one, and convey relevant political information to them.

6 HUMOUR AND PERSUASION

In addition to humour’s capacity to convey factual information, research has also paid heed to whether and how humour can persuade people. This is a broad question that can refer to different interconnected cognitive processes.

Findings on humour’s persuasion capacity, now in the sense of changing people’s already held opinions or attitudes, are mixed at best. According to research, the satirical programme *Zondag met Lubach* contributed to undermining support for right-wing populist actors among voters

already leaning towards these options by exposing the shortcomings of populist rhetoric^[108]. However, a study that capitalised on a public discussion forum that approximated ‘an ideal Habermasian communication situation’ and studied 46k posts and more than 3.5M comments, found that all types of illocutionary intents (to exchange ideas or information, to share a sense of belonging to the same group, to give emotional or practical aid, etc.) had ‘a significant association with the message being considered as view-changing, with the notable exception of *fun*’, which was defined as ‘experiencing leisure, laughter, and joy’^[109]. In a similar vein, research on the *perceived* effects of political satire yields somewhat contradictory results: whereas communication experts believe that satirical programmes can persuade people and influence their behaviour, ordinary citizens tend to reject this possibility^[105].

To complicate matters further, research also shows that different groups can react differently, sometimes in opposing ways, to the same humorous message^[110]. In this regard, it has been argued that we should ‘step away from the treatment of satire’, let alone humour, ‘as monolithic’^[103]. Unsurprisingly, when it comes to why different people react differently to the same message, already held beliefs and how humorous messages align with them play a major role^[76,103,110], in agreement with research on (failed) persuasion processes more generally^[111].

Studies on the mechanisms underpinning persuasion processes usually rely on experiments, which have been conducted outside the DELIAH countries. In a nutshell, they contend that the persuasive potential of a humorous message rests on its ability to disrupt people’s ability to counterargue, i.e., to critically examine the humorous message and formulate reasons against it. This is claimed to be the result of recipients investing much cognitive energy in understanding the humorous message^[103]. However, research also finds a message discounting effect, i.e., recipients fail to take the message seriously due to it being ‘just a joke’^[112]. This has led some scholars to speculate that humour might have a ‘sleeper effect’. That is, although it fails to exert any persuasive influence in the short term, the information conveyed by the humorous message can over time gain influence over recipients’ attitudes due to the message having been processed centrally^[99]. However, a meta-analysis of the literature has not found any consistent evidence of a sleeper effect^[113]. Furthermore, the study identified a ‘moderate-level effect’ on knowledge, a weak one on attitudes and behavioral intent, and nonsignificant effects on behavior, which were even weaker or nonexistent in the field of politics^[113]. All in all, ‘researchers have yet to find strong and consistent evidence of humor’s persuasive capacity’, as argued in another review of the literature^[104].

The argument thus far does not imply that humour cannot influence people in other ways, for example, through priming. Priming refers to *what* information is presented^[114]. Rather than encouraging people to modify the views they already hold, priming and related processes such as framing seek to influence what information happens to be at the top of people’s head when they make a political decision. For instance, communication can encourage people to think about security issues instead of economic ones when it comes to deciding what party to vote for, without this implying that they change their views on security issues or economic questions. The gateway effect discussed in the previous section attests to humour’s potential to prime people, i.e., to draw their attention to specific events or issues (e.g., an electoral debate), which can, in turn, lead to additional consequences (e.g., encourage people to vote)^[91,104,115]. Similarly, humour can draw audience attention to details, such as the flaws of a political candidate, which can have additional effects; e.g., that the candidate is seen as more relatable^[105]. In principle, any form of public communication can contribute to priming and framing. Hence, what effects humorous messages can achieve through these processes largely depends on the broader media environment and on people’s exposure to competing forms of priming and framing.

As argued in section 2, there is little research on the emotional dimension of humour and its effects. The available studies suggest that the feeling of mirth, a positive emotion associated with humour, can promote tolerance of deontological violations in the case of moral dilemmas^[20], while the so-called ‘affect-transfer process’, used in advertising, refers to humour’s emotional dimension influencing other elements by proximity, including other emotions (e.g., distress) emanating from competing messages^[91].

Finally, humour has been identified as a factor in contemporary processes of radicalisation. The extent to which humour practices contribute to these processes, or whether they rather reflect them, which can be traced back to cultural and economic change, including growing inequality^[16], is an open question. In any case, the available research suggests that humour is used to legitimate aggression^[28] and disseminate hate speech^[76], although both the actual persuasive effects of these humour practices and their underlying mechanisms remain unknown. Regarding the latter, it can be posited that the employment of humour may serve to problematise and gradually change the taken-for-granted world that underlies normative commitments. That is to say, the use of humour’s playful dimension (section 3) may be employed to challenge and shift what can be said and done in a socially acceptable way. However, more research is needed to examine whether this is indeed the mechanism at work. Importantly, research should also more clearly distinguish between opinion *change* and opinion *formation*, as the humour practices associated with radicalisation are likely to be more effective vis-à-vis (young) people with uncrystallised preferences than vis-à-vis people with crystallised ones.

Similarly, humour practices have been associated with the formation and maintenance of groups of like-minded individuals or echo chambers (see also section 4)^[44,68], where expressed opinions reinforce each other leading to the so-called *law of group polarisation*^[117]. This notwithstanding, additional research is required to clarify whether echo chambers, and the role of humour therein, serve to *change-cum-radicalise* opinions or to *form* them in the first place. Alternatively, they can contribute to *mobilising* people with already radicalised views, who now feel socially supported, or to influencing the range of opinions that get *publicly expressed*. These different mechanisms are not only important to better theorise humour, but they also have different implications for the formulation of effective counterstrategies.

7 HUMOUR FOR POLITICAL MOBILISATION AND PARTICIPATION

Politics is largely about (de-)mobilising people, whether that is to encourage them to vote, to demonstrate publicly, or, on the contrary, to motivate them to remain at home. This section discusses research related to political mobilisation, including the relationship between humour and micro-level factors that support citizen participation, as well as the use of humour by collective actors, in particular political parties and social movements, to mobilise people.

As regards individual-level factors, experimental research on subversive humour against sexism (Image 9) shows that it has a positive impact on the reported willingness of individuals with a less pronounced feminist identity to engage in collective action for gender equality^[118,119]. The size of the effect of humorous messages is similar to that of serious ones, but with the additional benefit that the former produce less overall aversiveness^[119], thus they reduce the risk of also mobilising political opponents. More generally, what this suggests, if read in connection with

the gateway effect discussed in sections 5 and 6, is that humour can be used to increase the (reported) disposition to participate in collective action among people with a *modest* degree of the attitude expressed by the humorous message. For those reporting stronger attitudes can be expected to be already inclined to participate and thus to remain unaffected by the humorous message, and those whose attitudes do not align with the humorous message are unlikely to be persuaded, as discussed in the previous section^[118,119].

Similarly, comparative research suggests that political entertainment media, including comedy news and political satire, can have a positive effect on citizens' internal political efficacy and thus on their likelihood of engaging in politics (Info Box 5). This can be due to these programmes' capacity to convey information in an accessible way^[120]. However, the empirical evidence is far from conclusive, and, more importantly, the relation of causality is unclear. In this regard, other studies suggest that political humour does not promote participation. Rather, it *attracts* people with a political interest, who are more likely to participate from the outset^[104].

Info Box 5

Political efficacy refers to the feeling that individual political action can have an influence over the political process^[120]. It comprises two dimensions, namely **internal** and **external political efficacy**. The former measures citizens' perception of their ability to participate in politics, while the latter designates the belief that the political system is responsive to the demands of the citizenry.

The expression **collective action** refers, in its broadest sense, to people working together to achieve some common goals. However, it is usually used to designate forms of cooperation that happen outside of existing institutions and formal organisations. In the context of politics, social movements, social mobilisations and collective protests are typical examples. There is a third meaning, which is associated with the pair **collective vs connective action**. In the context of this opposition, **collective action** designates a form of collective mobilisation 'associated with high levels of organizational resources' and the control of the action by organisations (e.g., trade unions, political parties) that appear in the foreground of the mobilising coalitions. **Connective action**, in turn, is 'based on personalized content sharing across media networks'. Usually, it takes the form of action enabled by organisations or a core of activists who stay in the background of the mobilising coalitions, encouraging individuals to adopt an active role by, among other things, re-appropriating, shaping and sharing themes^[121].

As regards the utilisation of humour by collective actors, research is surprisingly scarce and the gaps in the literature are remarkable. Nevertheless, there are some relatively consistent themes. Humour is frequently used to attract media and public attention, and to engage people. Moreover, it is often used to criticise political opponents and manage conflicts. However, when it comes to specifying these practices and their effects, details vary according to the actors analysed. Moreover, the lack of shared theoretical concepts and different research questions impede the formulation of an argument integrating the different findings.

Regarding the use of humour by (for the lack of a better term) *mainstream* political parties, the available studies describe the myriad humour practices associated with the theatricalisation and personalisation of politics (Image 10)^[122]. Additionally, they confirm candidates' growing participation in infotainment programmes and political parties' use of humorous communication strategies^[123,124]. In particular, research finds that self-deprecating humour on the part of a candidate can help her to project a relatable image and respond to criticism. Studies also emphasise the potential of humour to attract media coverage and shape the public discourse, including

drawing audience attention away from topics that could undermine electoral support^[123,124]. Finally, engaging in online humour practices and participating in infotainment shows is claimed to allow candidates to connect with and to mobilise younger voters.

Image 9

Source: ^[118]

Example of humor against sexism.

Image 10

Source: [aktuality.sk](https://www.aktuality.sk)

<https://www.aktuality.sk/clanok/200712/poslanci-sas-sa-vyzlekli-nielen-z-imunity>

Example of a burlesque performance reported in ^[122]. Members of the Slovak parliament, representing the Freedom and Solidarity party, stripped naked for a campaign to abolish parliamentary immunity. The banner reads: 'Let's strip MPs of their immunity'.

The online humour practices of authoritarian populist actors have also been the subject of some attention. Comparative research on this topic shows that antagonistic messages by these actors, including the use of sarcasm, result in higher levels of online engagement^[125] and more emotionally charged reactions^[126]. Notably, the emojis 'anger' and 'haha' are especially prevalent in them, and they are often interconnected: the latter typically signals sarcastic mockery of political adversaries, which in turn can lead to expressions of anger (Image 11)^[126].

Finally, research on social movements has paid attention to a broader range of issues. Social movements employ humour, for example by parodying advertising and other forms of mass communication, to expose inconsistencies in the hegemonic social order; to attract media coverage and disseminate information; to encourage onlookers to identify with the movement (not just due to the movement's message being 'funny', but also due to it being ambiguous); to relieve tensions after episodes of repression or conflict-ridden meetings; and to diffuse threatening situations or pre-emptively avoid hostile reactions by putting adversaries (e.g., police forces) in situations where the use of coercion would appear disproportionate^[71]. These uses of humour characterise contemporary social movements, but also earlier mobilisations^[79,127]. More recently, *connective* forms of mobilisation (Info Box 5) and organisational cultures emphasising participation and deemphasising ideological purity have been associated with the use of humour for novel goals. These include engaging activists in tasks deemed particularly boring, such as the writing of minutes (written as funny stories in the case of the Spanish 15M movement), and promoting creativity, for example, in the creation of slogans and banners^[71,128,129].

It should be emphasised that studies on social movements and mobilisations rely on activists' own accounts and the interpretation of their actions and messages. Hence, more research is needed to confirm that humour practices had the intended effects and, more importantly, to specify the conditions under which they have worked and failed. In this regard, an interesting question is whether the use of humour is constrained by the political context, such that growing levels of polarisation and political violence can be expected to result either in the decline of humour practices or in shifts towards more confrontational styles of humour. Contemporary and past research on social mobilisations suggests that this may be the case^[127,130], while this argument would also make sense vis-à-vis the popularity of ethnic humour in the Basque Country coinciding with the decline in terrorist activity^[82,131,132]. Whether or not the claim holds cannot be adjudicated with the available evidence. In any case, a careful reading of the arguments linking the use of humour and the political context suggests that expectations, in particular subjective assessments of how 'serious' (e.g., threatening) a situation has become, are likely to be more important than objective contextual features pertaining to levels of violence or ideological polarisation.

Image 11

Source: ^[126] / Geert Wilders' Facebook page (21/01/2018) Combination of 'anger' and 'haha' reactions to Geert Wilders' Facebook post. The text reads: 'Eight Eritreans in a drunken state. Probably on the way to the New Year's drink of D'66 Amsterdam at the invitation of Alexander Penthouse', with the headline of the news article reading 'Police takes drunken migrant from truck at highway truck stop: "They consumed some of the beer being transported"^[126].

8 HUMOUR AND THE DEMOCRATIC DEBATE

Contemporary democratic theory emphasises political preference formation as one of the key elements to assess the democratic quality of a political system. In this regard, the public sphere is expected to fulfil different functions, one of which is to enable the exchange of reasons on political topics, which favours the dissemination of relevant information, the critical scrutiny of arguments and the concomitant filtering out or revision of political preferences that are based on discredited arguments and evidence (Info Box 6).

Along these lines, satirical TV shows like *Zondag met Lubach* have been shown to have a positive impact on viewers' knowledge of specific policy issues, increasing audience's perceived understanding of them, and enhancing their salience in the public debate^[96]. Other satirical shows, such as *Tujurikkuja*^[60], and humour practices more generally^[59] have also shown a comparable capacity to influence the public conversation. By capitalising on humour's playful nature, comedy programmes have successfully enriched the public debate by extending criticism to groups that had remained off limits of the public discourse, while giving voice to marginalised groups, and reaching audiences that feel less attracted to other content, especially young people^[81,82]. Similarly, online humorous communication^[44,133,134] can reach and engage new participants, sometimes resulting in platforms like Zomri, which has become a notable actor in Slovak public debate^[98,135,136]. Enabling the inclusion of new voices implies that humour, especially online^[44,134],

allows the expression of dissent and the articulation of unpopular and shocking views, which also contributes to an inclusive democratic dialogue, as recognised by the European Court of Justice^[137]. Importantly, humour also allows these views to be expressed in an approachable way^[134]. Finally, humour practices are also used to spark critical reflection^[8,138,139].

Info Box 6

Deliberation refers to ‘a dialogical process of exchanging reasons for the purpose of resolving problematic situations that cannot be settled without interpersonal coordination and cooperation’^[140]. According to the dominant approach to democracy in contemporary political theory, namely deliberative democratic theory, these processes are fundamental to any democracy in order to live up to its most fundamental normative promises. These are usually identified with the principle of equal liberty or with the promise of being an epistemically superior (i.e., more intelligent) form of government.

Although there are some controversies over what deliberation entails, and where and how it should take place, there is widespread agreement that the **public sphere** ought to play a major role in these enlightening public debates. More specifically, the public sphere can be defined as ‘a theater in modern societies in which political participation is enacted through the medium of talk. It is the space in which citizens deliberate about their common affairs, hence, an institutionalized arena of discursive interaction’^[141]. This definition captures a tension within actually existing public spheres, which are torn between ideals of deliberation and performances of participation through talk, which do not aim at ‘coordination and cooperation’.

Examples of Humorous Messages Encouraging Reflection and Expressing Social Criticism:

‘What annoys me about extreme forms of wokeness is that I notice that all around me average people are dropping out. I hear people saying things like: “What’s with all this woke nonsense? I’m sure discrimination is not that bad.” No! Those two are completely independent of one another. One is people seeking attention, and the other is a real societal issue. But I get how people get angry by such extremism, but I think the solution lies not with getting riled up, the solution lies within ourselves.’ (Michael Van Peel in the special *Welcome to the Rebellion!*, 2022, cited in ^[138])

‘Oddly enough, a young man who does not allow himself to be manipulated by anyone defends the same ideas as the three richest men in the world’. This is the headline of a ‘news’ story published by the satirical magazine *EIMundoToday*, with the subtitle: ‘Coincidentally, freedom on social media has led him to the same ideology as the owners of these social networks’.

<https://www.elmundotoday.com/2025/01/curiosamente-un-joven-que-no-se-deja-manipular-por-nadie-defiende-las-mismas-ideas-que-los-tres-hombres-mas-ricos-del-mundo/>

Despite these contributions of humour to democratic debate, humorous communication often plays a more limited role or a more ambiguous one, and it can sometimes have an outright undemocratic influence. First, humour practices have lately been associated with so-called ‘humour scandals’^[59,142] or similar phenomena like ‘political-moral panics’^[143]. Although they can be interpreted as ‘precipitating events’ that stimulate public discussion^[144], these scandals often reactivate political coalitions and discourses along established political divisions, thus contributing little to the expression of new views or arguments^[143]. In this regard, they have been claimed to reinforce ‘existing power relations’^[142], which is consistent with the idea that much

political humour simply repeats common-sense views^[145]. Having said that, controversies surrounding humour practices can also have unintended consequences in the form of, e.g., new legal developments^[137,146].

Online humour practices have also attracted considerable scholarly attention, which has consistently emphasised their multifaceted role in the public debate. In this regard, online humour practices related to the Covid-19 pandemic, which evolved from having an expressive function to being toxic and polarising and expressing cynicism^[44], illustrate this ambiguity. More generally, research consistently supports the ideas that online humour provides a form of participation for, in particular, young people, but not exclusively to them. Second, it mostly serves an expressive function. In other words, it enables the expression of anger, frustration, amazement, etc., and thereby provides emotional relief (images 12 and 13), or it serves to communicate preferences, but it often fails to provide detailed justifications for them (Image 14)^[49,147-152].

Image 12

Source: ^[150]
'Parents waiting for the government to announce that schools will be reopened' during the Covid-19 pandemic^[150].

Image 13

Source: ^[150]
Meme alluding to homeschooling during the Covid-19 pandemic. It features 'well-known characters from the Estonian children's TV programme *Buratino tegutseb jälle*. *Me graduating from high school / My mom graduating from high school*'^[150].

Image 14

Source: ^[63] / Movimiento de Liberación Gráfica Madrid
The meme reads: 'Madrid deserves Manuela. And you know it'. Manuela Carmena was a candidate for Mayor of Madrid.

Moreover, many online humour practices seem to be primarily motivated by the desire to have fun. These include trolling^[153], much of the humorous communication about politicians' private lives^[154], and, tellingly, much of the humorous communication sparked by electoral debates^[155,156]. In these cases, humour practices serve entertainment purposes, but they usually focus on anecdotes and fail to convey relevant political content.

Finally, a significant amount of the humorous messages that circulate online are used to exclude specific groups of people, undermine efforts to include them, or spread distrust (Image 15)^[28,44,68]. They also often convey hate speech directly^[74-76], and in extreme cases they can encourage people to participate in acts of sabotage (Image 16)^[44].

Image 15

Source: ^[44] / verhalenbank.nl
<http://www.verhalenbank.nl/items/show/129181>
'Bill Gates wants to control and kill people by putting nano chips in his vaccine' ^[44].

Image 16

Source: ^[44] / verhalenbank.nl
<https://www.verhalenbank.nl/items/show/129166>
Meme linking the Covid pandemic with the 5G network.

Importantly, these expressive, entertaining, and harmful humour practices, which do not live up to the normative expectations of democratic public spheres, can contribute to diffuse processes of opinion and collective will formation by altering the cultural repertoires (composed of, e.g., shared narratives, frames, symbols, etc.) on which social actors draw to communicate publicly. From a democratic theory perspective, their assessment largely depends on the specific content of these cultural elements and how they are subsequently used. This notwithstanding, some theoretical arguments have been formulated about the democratic value of some cultural forms. For example, about the benefits of irony over alternative genres in social narratives^[35,157,158]. Consistent empirical evidence supporting these arguments is still lacking.

9 HUMOUR AND THE IMPLEMENTATION OF POLITICAL DECISIONS

Almost no research has been conducted on how humour is used to enforce political decisions, let alone its effects. This is a substantial gap, as there are plenty of examples of public authorities using humorous communication to disseminate information and nudge citizens—recently, for instance, EU Commissioner Hadja Lahbib’s video on the so-called Preparedness Strategy.

Interestingly, the few studies on this topic draw attention to citizens’ practices of co-education (or social control) and civil society’s contribution to implementing specific decisions. Regarding the former, Covid-19-related memes in the Netherlands during the Spring of 2020 lockdown became an exercise in ‘disciplining and distinction’, where behaviours, such as the amassing of toilet paper, were mocked while others were celebrated (Image 17)^[159]. As regards civil society’s participation in the enforcement of decisions, examples can be found in Estonia, where humour has been deployed as part of its soft-security and civic resilience strategy in response to heightened Russian disinformation since 2022. A key actor in this context is Propastop, an independ-

ent blog run by the Estonian Defence League volunteers and dedicated to exposing anti-Estonian propaganda^[160]. It sometimes reacts with memes to what is deemed disinformation and foreign involvement (Image 18).

Image 17

Source: ^[159] / Twitter, VVD (10 March 2020)
A meme about then-Dutch prime minister Mark Rutte, who had just announced one should not shake hands.

Image 18

Source: propastop.org
<https://www.propastop.org/en/2025/02/11/baltics-cut-the-cord-russia-reacts-to-brell-exit/>
In 2025, Estonia, Latvia, and Lithuania disconnected from the Russian-controlled BRELL (Belarus-Russia-Estonia-Latvia-Lithuania) energy ring, marking a major step in their long-planned energy independence from Moscow. In response to Russian propaganda and aggressive memes about the disconnection, Propastop reacted with memes like this one.

Image 19

Source: ^[161]
Sign in a bus stop. It reads: 'Dear masks, please put on a Berliner!'

Image 20

Source: Visit Berlin / CNN
<https://edition.cnn.com/travel/article/berlin-coronavirus-ad-finger/index.html>
Advert used by the authorities of Berlin. It reads: 'Up yours to those who don't wear a mask—we obey the corona rules'.

Concerning the use of humour by public authorities, the only study available for the DELIAH countries focuses on the case of Berlin during the Covid-19 pandemic. Compliance with the prescribed hygienic measures was encouraged by the use of humorous signs that sought not only to convey relevant information about what should (not) be done, but also to foster a sense of community through the use of group-specific cultural codes, including codes deemed distinctive of Berlin and its sense of humour (images 19 and 20)^[161].

The effectiveness of all these humorous interventions is yet to be measured.

10 HUMOUR AND ACCOUNTABILITY

According to standard (i.e., principal-agent) representation theory, accountability refers to a type of relationship in which public representatives and public authorities can be forced to explain their actions and citizens have powers to sanction and reward them. The available literature identifies three major themes in this context; namely, how social actors use humour to draw attention to behaviours and outcomes that need to be explained, how political elites use humour to hold each other accountable, and how representatives use humour to escape accountability.

From the point of view of social actors, including mass media, humour practices usually focus on the credibility and moral authority of representatives and decision-makers. This notwithstanding, satirical shows and magazines provide ample space for the humorous treatment of policy decisions and political events^[36,162], which have also been the target of some humour online practices, especially during the Covid-19 pandemic^[44,149]. More frequently, humour practices, including subtle ones^[91] (section 2), address aspects of politicians public persona. While they sometimes mock behaviours and physical traits weakly related, if at all, to actual political performance^[72,154], a common theme is the use of humour to denounce representatives' inconsistent behaviour^[163] and their alleged weakness or incompetence^[164], even if the latter topic appears intermingled with aspects like their physical appearance or ethnic background^[165] (images 21 and 22).

The holding of regular elections encourages political elites to control each other. In this regard, research on humour and accountability among elites is scarce in the DELIAH countries. It suggests, first, that the pairing of (serious) political attacks with other-deprecatory humour, i.e., humour targeting opponents, reduces the likelihood of these attacks backfiring against the person delivering it^[166]. Second, it contends that the use of humour by authoritarian populist actors, specifically those in the Flemish parliament at the beginning of the 21st century, served to discredit the political establishment rather than address policy concerns^[166] or outscore specific adversaries^[167].

Image 21

Source: Zomri

<https://www.facebook.com/photo.php?fbid=1838661036413151&id=1729940727285183&set=a.1730233777255878>

Meme created in response to an incident in which two far-right politicians were photographed ordering dinner in a Turkish restaurant serving kebab. It features the leader of the party People's Party Our Slovakia with the slogan 'For God and for Kebab! (in a bun and extra chilli)'. The meme plays with the words *strana* (party) and *sranda* (fun)—hence, it reads 'On March 5, vote for Kotleba – People's Fun Our Slovakia'.

Image 22

Source: Zomri

<https://www.zomri.online/2017/07/23/takto-to-bolo/>

It reads: 'The secret map of the route to Kryvá'n revealed. This is how it was!' This meme alludes to an incident in June 2017 involving members of *Kotleba – People's Party Our Slovakia* who climbed the wrong *Kriváň*, not the one that is widely regarded as a national symbol of Slovakia. The serious orthographic mistakes (*Kryvá'n* instead of *Kriváň*) hints at the paradox of self-proclaimed patriots who do not master the Slovak language.

Finally, research has paid some attention to representatives' use of humour to escape accountability. In this respect, it contends that engaging in 'pure' forms of humour, i.e., seemingly apolitical ones like TV comedy shows^[124], and the use of self-deprecatory humour about trivial actions or facts (e.g., on weight loss)^[72] contribute to shaping media coverage in such a way that deeper scrutiny is sidestepped. Importantly, research also draws attention (in passing) to the backlash that humour practices by elites can produce, as comedy is sometimes perceived as too frivolous an issue for public representatives^[66].

11 SOCIAL GROUPS' RELATIONSHIP WITH HUMOUR

As argued in section 2, research on humour and politics often relies on small-N or case studies that pay little attention to how social groups use and react to humour. This is especially the case of groups defined according to sociodemographic variables. That said, the distribution of entries in D1.1 and the historical accounts provided by some studies^[168,169] suggest that there has been a growing societal acceptance of humorous and entertaining cultural products. In addition, recent 'connective' forms of mobilisation and more participatory organisational cultures have been associated with an intensified and more strategic use of humour, particularly among social movements (section 7), while the advent of social media has extended the range of humour practices, which now incorporate memes, and forms of civic engagement available to the citizenry. They are especially used by young people and groups engaging in harmful humour (sections 2 and 8).

Consistent with research on people's cognitive biases^[111], the studies reviewed also suggest that humour appreciation is associated with recipients' previous beliefs and attitudes, so that people prefer and judge as less harmful those humour practices that align with their attitudes or with their social positions (e.g., men find man-disparagement humour less funny than women

do)^[76,170]. Drawing on this finding, it is possible to partly fill in the gap in the humour and politics literature by taking insights from research on political cleavages (Info Box 7). According to it, harmful forms of humour, associated with sexism, racism, ethno-nationalism, and authoritarianism, are likely to resonate among so-called ‘white school leavers’, i.e., ‘white voters who leave formal education with the lowest level of qualifications or no qualifications at all’^[171], as well as among people living in rural areas, particularly ‘left-behind’ areas, i.e., regions or communities experiencing economic decline and social stagnation. Conversely, women, non-heterosexuals, university graduates, and urban dwellers are less likely to engage in or react positively to harmful forms of humour^[116,171-173]. While these relationships between social groups and forms of humour can be formulated as hypotheses, the available research also suggests that this is probably an oversimplification. For one thing, because it is unclear that there is a crystallised cleavage structure in Europe^[174] and, even if there were, that it applies to all European countries. Second, there is evidence that non-political variables, such as familiarity with the cultural codes of memes, also influence humour appreciation^[76].

Info Box 7

Cleavages are social divisions along which political preferences are structured. They comprise three elements: (1) social groups defined according to socio-structural criteria like ethnicity, gender, and education level, who express (2) distinctive political preferences, at least on specific topics, which are represented by (3) specific political organisations, usually distinct party families.

Moreover, research on ethnic humour in Spain finds that people in peripheral regions are more familiar with, and more likely to appreciate, humour about their own social, political, or ethnic characteristics than those in central regions^[139,175]. At least two complementary explanations can be offered. First, to the extent that people in peripheral regions identify with a position that is more incongruent with the social majority, they are more likely to recognise and play with their own incongruity, as well as that of the social majority^[175]. Second, self-parody can be a strategy to carve out a position of enunciation that enables them to be publicly accepted and heard (section 4). These arguments can, in principle, be extended to other non-dominant social groups and their practices of re-appropriating cultural elements (discussed in section 4). Consequently, it can be hypothesised that humour and humour appreciation depend on whether social groups are dominant or marginalised. Marginalised groups are likely to be more sensitive to harmful humour from dominant groups, but they are also more likely to engage in and appreciate self-parody. Dominant groups can be expected to downplay harmful humour and engage in other-deprecatory, rather than self-deprecating, humour. It should be emphasised that these are hypotheses, which draw on available research, but which go beyond what the studies actually show. Furthermore, the interaction between these variables and previous ones is underdetermined, especially when subjects are placed in socially dominant positions due to certain characteristics, yet other sociodemographic variables place them in non-dominant positions (as with women living in central regions).

12 STRATEGIES AGAINST HARMFUL HUMOUR

Despite some exceptions^[176], very little research has been conducted on strategies specifically targeting harmful humour. Studies mostly address humorous communication as part of the broader question of how to deal with hate speech and exclusionary communication, or they just gloss over humour in discussing how to combat hate speech and related phenomena. In addition, research paying attention to harmful humour concludes that counterstrategies have been ineffective or counterproductive, or that there is insufficient information to assess their effectiveness^[87], which is consistent with the state of research in related fields, such as prejudice reduction^[177]. The absence of effective countermeasures has been traced back to the still insufficient understanding of the social groups engaging in exclusionary communication, their audiences, and their sub-cultures^[87], which has been recently corroborated by research on the manosphere in the UK. Among other things, it draws attention to the ‘nuanced, fragmented landscape with conflicting sub-cultures and ideologies’ of the manosphere^[178]. Similarly, research on online misinformation confirms a pattern of heterogeneous behaviours and orientations among internet users. For example, it shows that a relatively small number of users produce and share most of the content, while a significantly larger number only share a few posts. Meanwhile, most users simply consume this content and display varying degrees of scepticism towards it^[119,179,180].

Moreover, section 6 on persuasion has already clarified the extent to which humour can be expected to play a role in spreading exclusionary and anti-democratic views. In this regard, if harmful humour is interpreted in the broader context of affective polarisation and the mobilisation of authoritarian populist actors, the available evidence suggests that this type of humour is rooted in discontent caused by actual processes of cultural and economic change^[116,171–173], rather than being primarily the result of freely-floating messages and flows of online communication. Accordingly, countermeasures targeting communication alone are likely to be insufficient.

However, this does not imply that humorous communication plays no role in disseminating hate speech and antidemocratic attitudes, nor that counterstrategies targeting harmful humour are futile. As elaborated in sections 5 to 7, humour can have a gateway effect. In other words, while it is unlikely to change the crystallised opinions of people, it can help to activate and consolidate the latent extremist beliefs of some individuals or contribute to the formation of specific attitudes among those with no clear views on a given topic. Hence, harmful humour can have an insidious effect, particularly among young people. Counterstrategies should thus focus on this particular social group^[176].

Possible countermeasures include judicial oversight^[181] and content moderation by social media companies^[182,183], which are discussed in more detail in other working packages of the DELIAH project. Here, we focus on additional measures that can be implemented by civil society actors. In this respect, the available literature identifies some pitfalls that should be avoided. First, the amplification of the harmful content when denouncing it^[176]. Second, overreacting to harmful humour, which can be easily reinterpreted as a sign of intolerance, social conformity, or ‘wokeness’; in short, can be used to draw attention to the alleged authoritarian practices of liberal democrats. Furthermore, overreactions are likely to amplify the toxic message^[176]. Third, harsh public condemnations can also backfire by encouraging people to counterargue and stick more firmly to their views^[184].

Bearing this in mind, two different sets of promising counterstrategies can be identified. The first includes measures that can be implemented on delimited groups of people, such as those in educational contexts. They reduce the risk of amplifying humorous hate speech and overreacting to harmful humour, as they consist of scripted interventions. Potential counterstrategies can take inspiration from, for example, the non-judgemental exchange of narratives; namely, ‘a strategy where an individual attempts to persuade another person by providing to or eliciting from them narratives about relevant personal experiences while non-judgmentally listening to the views they express’^[184,185]. The goal of the intervention is to encourage perspective-taking and so-called self-persuasion, which has been shown to durably change people’s attitudes^[185]. While not specifically targeting harmful humour practices or people engaged in them, this countermeasure can address harmful humour’s negative consequences in the form of antidemocratic and exclusionary attitudes among young people.

Similarly, ‘edutainment’ has yielded promising results in combatting misinformation^[186] and it could be investigated whether edutainment, including forms of counter-humour, could be leveraged for democratic education. Working Package 8 of the DELIAH project addresses this issue in more detail.

Additionally, interventions aimed at young people should raise awareness of how harmful humour surreptitiously shapes attitudes and public debate. The dissemination of this information is implied by the normative content of democracy, including the principle of equal liberty^[187], which this form of government can be expected to honour and foster through democratic, i.e., liberty-promoting, education.

Although the available empirical evidence shows that people are usually capable of identifying hate speech when it is presented as humour^[76], it is also the case that humour can rely on cultural codes that are not widely understood (section 4). Accordingly, interventions on young people can be paired with the dissemination of information (e.g., on specific images, expressions, and fora) to help parents quickly identify potentially harmful content in their children’s online activity.

The second set of possible counterstrategies is supplementary and wider in scope. It aims to change the cultural repertoire, particularly the narratives and frames used by social actors to publicly express their grievances and preferences. In this regard, some scholars (from outside the humour and politics field) advocate producing and disseminating alternative, more inclusionary narratives through which the grievances currently expressed through conspiracy theories, hate speech, etc., can be conveyed in a less toxic manner^[40,188–190]. These interventions do not directly engage with harmful humour or other forms of antidemocratic and exclusionary speech, which runs the risk of amplifying their content and producing backlash. Instead, they strive to expand the cultural repertoire so that people can find new and less toxic ways of expressing their demands. This requires collaboration with influential social and political actors engaged or willing to engage in this activity, such as civil society organisations, artists, people in the cultural industries, and political parties.

REFERENCES

1. Engelken-Jorge M, Moreno C, Castañeda-Zumeta A, Astapova A, Bricker A, Cingerova N, et al. Humour practices and European attitudes towards democracy - data documentation. 2025. DOI:10.5281/zenodo.15756409
2. United Nations. United Nations Strategy and Plan of Action on Hate Speech. 2019. Available from: https://www.un.org/en/genocideprevention/documents/advising-and-mobilizing/Action_plan_on_hate_speech_EN.pdf
3. United Nations (General Assembly). International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights. Treaty Series1966;999:171.
4. Warren ME. A Problem-Based Approach to Democratic Theory. *American Political Science Review* 2017;111(1):39–53. DOI:10.1017/S0003055416000605
5. Thelwall M, Sud P. Scopus 1900–2020: Growth in articles, abstracts, countries, fields, and journals. *Quantitative Science Studies* 2022;3(1):37–50. DOI:10.1162/qss_a_00177
6. Schermer JA, Rogoza R, Kwiatkowska MM, Kowalski CM, Aquino S, Ardi R, et al. Humor styles across 28 countries. *Current Psychology* 2023;42(19):16304–19. DOI:10.1007/s12144-019-00552-y
7. Kfrerer ML, Bell E, Schermer JA. The politics of being funny: Humor styles, trait humorousness, and political orientations. *Pers Individ Dif* 2021;182:111073. DOI:10.1016/j.paid.2021.111073
8. Meyer JC. Humor as a Double-Edged Sword: Four Functions of Humor in Communication. *Communication Theory* 2000;10(3):310–31. DOI:10.1111/j.1468-2885.2000.tb00194.x
9. Garin M, Pérez-Pamies D. Power and satire in the front-page images of Mariano Rajoy: visual motifs as political humour. *European Journal of Humour Research* 2021;9(3):65–91. DOI:10.7592/EJHR2021.9.3.534
10. Tilly C. *Contention and Democracy in Europe, 1650–2000*. Cambridge University Press; 2004. DOI:10.1017/CBO9780511756092
11. Hobbes T, Molesworth W. *The English Works of Thomas Hobbes of Malmesbury / Vol. 4, Human Nature, or The Fundamental Elements of Policy Being a Discovery of the Faculties, Acts and Passions of the Soul of a Man*. London: J. Bohn; 1840.
12. Schopenhauer A. *The World as Will and Presentation*. Abingdon: Routledge; 2016.
13. Martin RA, Ford TE. *The Psychology of Humor: An Integrative Approach*. London: Elsevier; 2018. DOI:10.1016/C2016-0-03294-1
14. Biemans WG, Huizingh EKRE. Why so serious? The effects of humour on creativity and innovation. *Creativity and Innovation Management* 2024;33(2):181–96. DOI:10.1111/caim.12587
15. Freud S. *The joke and its relation to the unconscious*. London: Penguin Books; 2003.
16. Tavory I. The situations of culture: Humor and the limits of measurability. *Theory Soc* 2014;43(3):275–89. DOI:10.1007/s11186-014-9222-7
17. Luhmann N. What is Communication? *Communication Theory* 1992;2(3):251–9. DOI:10.1111/j.1468-2885.1992.tb00042.x
18. Carroll N. *Humour: A Very Short Introduction*. Oxford: Oxford University Press; 2014.

19. Friedman S. The cultural currency of a ‘good’ sense of humour: British comedy and new forms of distinction. *Br J Sociol* 2011;62(2):347–70. DOI:10.1111/j.1468-4446.2011.01368.x
20. Strohminger N, Lewis RL, Meyer DE. Divergent effects of different positive emotions on moral judgment. *Cognition* 2011;119(2):295–300. DOI:10.1016/j.cognition.2010.12.012
21. Roseman IJ, Mattes K, Redlawsk DP, Katz S. Reprehensible, Laughable: The Role of Contempt in Negative Campaigning. *American Politics Research* 2020;48(1):44–77. DOI:10.1177/1532673X19857968
22. Pérez R. *The Souls of White Jokes: How Racist Humor Fuels White Supremacy*. Stanford: Stanford University Press; 2022.
23. Collier D, Jr. JEM. Conceptual “Stretching” Revisited: Adapting Categories in Comparative Analysis. *American Political Science Review* 1993;87(4):845–55. DOI:10.2307/2938818
24. Morreall J. Philosophy of Humor. In: Zalta EN, Nodelman U, editors. *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy*. 2024. Available from: <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/fall2024/entries/humor/>
25. Morreall J. No Laughing Matter: The Traditional Rejection of Humor and Traditional Theories of Humor. In: *Comic Relief: A Comprehensive Philosophy of Humor*. Chichester: John Wiley & Sons, Ltd; 2009. page 1–26. DOI:10.1002/9781444307795.ch1
26. Douglas M. The Social Control of Cognition: Some Factors in Joke Perception. *Man* 1968;3(3):361.
27. García A. Memes y Políticas de Identidad. El poder de la risa en la cultura digital. *Arte y Políticas de Identidad* 2020;23:144–62. DOI:10.6018/reapi.461201
28. García-Mingo E, Fernández SD, Tomás-Forte S. (Re)configuring the sexual violence imaginary from an antifeminist perspective: the ideological work of the Spanish manosphere. *Politica y Sociedad* 2022;59(1). DOI:10.5209/poso.80369
29. Alexander JC. *The Civil Sphere*. Oxford: Oxford University Press; 2006.
30. Fominaya CF. The Role of Humour in the Process of Collective Identity Formation in Autonomous Social Movement Groups in Contemporary Madrid. *Int Rev Soc Hist* 2007;52(S15):243–58. DOI:10.1017/S0020859007003227
31. Brubaker R, Cooper F. Beyond “identity.” *Theory Soc* 2000;29(1):1–47. DOI:10.1023/A:1007068714468
32. Tilly C. *Stories, identities, and political change*. Maryland: Rowman & Littlefield; 2002.
33. Lamont M, Molnár V. The study of boundaries in the social sciences. *Annu Rev Sociol* 2002;28:167–95. DOI:10.1146/annurev.soc.28.110601.141107
34. Wimmer A. The Making and Unmaking of Ethnic Boundaries: A Multilevel Process Theory. *American Journal of Sociology* 2008;113(4):970–1022. DOI:10.1086/522803
35. Engelken-Jorge M, Forchtner B, Özvatan Ö. Theorizing exclusionary and inclusionary people-making: from narrative genres to collective learning processes. *Distinktion: Journal of Social Theory* 2024;25(3):386–405. DOI:10.1080/1600910X.2023.2219416
36. Marín-Arrese JI. Cognition and culture in political cartoons. *Intercultural Pragmatics* 2008;5(1):1–18. DOI:10.1515/IP.2008.001

37. Valhondo JL. Parodic satire of no-do in polònia: Iconoclasm and visual re-framing of the spanish (far)right-wing discourse. *Communication and Society* 2021;34(2):417-32. DOI:10.15581/003.34.2.417-432
38. Wennekes E. Harassing Hogwash Scored with Happy Hardcore: The Ruthless Humor of the Dutch New Kids Films. In: *The Palgrave Handbook of Music in Comedy Cinema*. Springer International Publishing; 2023. page 397-413.
39. Vanlee F, Van Bauwel S, Dhaenens F. Distinctively queer in the Parish: Performances of distinction and LGBTQ plus representations in Flemish prestige television fiction. *European Journal of Cultural Studies* 2020;23(4):548-63. DOI:10.1177/1367549418821844
40. Lamont M. *Seeing others: How to redefine worth in a divided world*. London: Penguin Books; 2025.
41. Jammaers E, van Eck D, Cinque S. Embodying wilfulness: Investigating the unequal power dynamics of informal organisational body work through the case of women in stand-up comedy. *Human Relations* 2024;1-27. DOI:10.1177/00187267241288685
42. Brekhus W. *Culture and Cognition: Patterns in the Social Construction of Reality*. Cambridge: Polity Press; 2015.
43. Kuipers G. The difference between a Surinamese and a Turk: Ethnic jokes and the position of ethnic minorities in the Netherlands. *Humor - International Journal of Humor Research* 2000;13(2). DOI:10.1515/humr.2000.13.2.141
44. Meder T. Online Coping with the First Wave: Covid Humor and Rumor on Dutch Social Media (March - July 2020). *Folklore: Electronic Journal of Folklore* 2021;82:135-58. DOI:10.7592/FEJF2021.82.meder
45. Aksyutina O. Migration policy and the criminalization of protest. In: Loyd JM, Mitchelson M, Burridge A, editors. *Beyond Walls and Cages : Prisons, Borders, and Global Crisis*. University of Georgia Press; 2012. page 105-14.
46. Creten S, Heynderickx P, Dieltjens S. The Stigma Toward Dementia on Twitter: A Sentiment Analysis of Dutch Language Tweets. *J Health Commun* 2022;27(10):697-705. DOI:10.1080/10810730.2022.2149904
47. Gómez Morales B. “Esto con Franco no pasaba”: El franquismo en la comedia televisiva española. *Hispanic Research Journal* 2021;22(1):84-99. DOI:10.1080/14682737.2021.1982523
48. Rubio GC, Fiadotava A, Laineste L. “Laughter and Sex Prolong Life”: Current Trends in the Humour Practices of Russian-Speakers in Estonia. *Journal of Ethnology and Folkloristics* 2023;17(2):176-203. DOI:10.2478/jef-2023-0024
49. Laineste L, Voolaid P. Laughing across borders: Intertextuality of internet memes. *The European Journal of Humour Research* 2016;4(4):26-49. DOI:10.7592/EJHR2016.4.4.laineste
50. Nissenbaum A, Shifman L. Laughing alone, together: local user-generated satirical responses to a global event. *Inf Commun Soc* 2022;25(7):924-41. DOI:10.1080/1369118X.2020.1804979
51. Suárez- Romero M. El humor gráfico como herramienta de crítica: los líderes políticos internacionales en las viñetas de El País. *IC Revista Científica de Información y Comunicación* 2015,(12):227-55. DOI:10.12795/IC.2015.i01.08

52. Zürn M. *A Theory of Global Governance: Authority, Legitimacy, and Contestation*. Oxford: Oxford University Press; 2018.
53. Buzan B. *Making Global Society: A Study of Humankind Across Three Eras*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press; 2023.
54. Martínez-Quiroga P. Humor, feminismo y crítica social en la novela española contemporánea. *Bulletin of Spanish Studies* 2015;92(6):931–49. DOI:10.1080/14753820.2014.947854
55. Méndez García de Paredes E. “Mujeres alteradas”. La autoironía de grupo como liberación de tabúes femeninos. *Discurso & Sociedad* 2015;9(1):71–95.
56. Lion A. ‘I Need the White Pill!’ – A Creative Exploration of How Minority Flemish Youth Employ Ethnic Humour for Identity Construction. *Cult Sociol* 2024;1–20. DOI:10.1177/17499755241266867
57. Lion A, Dhaenens F. ‘Just kidding?’ An exploratory audience study into the ways Flemish youth with a minoritized ethnic identity make sense of ethnic humor and the politics of offense. *Humor* 2023;36(3):375–95. DOI:10.1515/humor-2022-0119
58. Nwankwo I. Dismantling Colonial Laughter: Tracing Emergent African Diaspora Stand-Up Comedy in French and German. *J Black Stud* 2024;55(8):638–60. DOI:10.1177/00219347241275140
59. Fatehi E, Juha H, Joonas K, and Laineste L. National identity through the prism of satire: humor scandals in Estonia 1991–2022. *J Balt Stud* 2025;1–22. DOI:10.1080/01629778.2025.2460503
60. Roos LL. ‘It is so bad to be Estonian:’ parody music videos and remediated sites of national cultural memory on Estonian public broadcasting. *J Balt Stud* 2023;54(2):377–94. DOI:10.1080/01629778.2022.2067578
61. Voolaid P. ‘The national sport of Estonia’: From big narratives to variegated and humorous/ironic colloquial rhetoric. *Maetagus* 2017;69:109–32. DOI:10.7592/MT2017.69.voolaid
62. van Kempen M. Dutch Tulips in Unexpected Colours: Humour in Dutch Migrant Writing: Kader Abdolah, Sevtap Baycılı, Khalid Boudou, Edgar Cairo. In: Dunphy G, Emig R, editors. *Hybrid humour: comedy in transcultural perspectives*. Leiden: Brill Academic Publishers; 2010. page 85–112. DOI:10.1163/9789042028241_005
63. Doncel EB. Circulación de memes en WhatsApp: ambivalencias del humor desde la perspectiva de género. *Empiria* 2016;(35):21–45. DOI:10.5944/EMPIRIA.35.2016.17167
64. Coleman JK. Privileging the Oriental in Paco Bezerra’s *El señor Ye ama los dragones*. *Symposium - Quarterly Journal in Modern Literatures* 2018;72(1):3–12. DOI:10.1080/00397709.2018.1421826
65. Posey A. ‘¿Tengo que comer gato?’ Racial stereotype in Quan Zhou Wu’s *Gente de aquí. Gente de allí*. *Ensayo gráfico sobre migrantes y españoles*. *Roman Notes* 2023;62(2):489–500. DOI:10.1353/RMC.2023.A919739
66. Nouws B. Roaring laughter in parliament. ‘De bulderlach van het halfroond’: Vlaamse parlementaire humor in historisch perspectief. *Journal of Belgian History / Revue belge d’histoire contemporaine / Belgisch tijdschrift voor nieuwste geschiedenis* 2017;47(1):10–35.
67. Zijp D. Comic innocence. *European Journal of Humour Research* 2024;12(1):116–34. DOI:10.7592/EJHR2024.12.1.837
68. Verhoeven E. Bonding over bashing: Discussing LGBTI topics in far-right alternative news media comments sections. *Communications* 2024. DOI:10.1515/commun-2023-0084/html

69. Díaz-Fernández S, García-Mingo E. The bar of Forocoches as a masculine online place: Affordances, masculinist digital practices and trolling. *New Media Soc* 2024;26(9):5336–58. DOI:10.1177/14614448221135631
70. T Hart M. Humour and Social Protest: An Introduction. *Int Rev Soc Hist* 2007;52(S15):1–20. DOI:10.1017/S0020859007003094
71. Romanos E. “No es una crisis, es que ya no te quiero”. Humor y protesta en el movimiento 15M. *Rev Int Sociol* 2016;74(3):e039. DOI:10.3989/ris.2016.74.3.039
72. Van Hout T, Burger P. Text bite news: The metapragmatics of feature news. *Text and Talk* 2017;37(4):461–84. DOI:10.1515/text-2017-0015
73. Bernardez-Rodal A, Rey PR, Franco YG. Radical right parties and anti-feminist speech on Instagram: Vox and the 2019 Spanish general election. *Party Politics* 2022;28(2):272–83. DOI:10.1177/1354068820968839
74. Martínez-Sanz R, Durántez-Stolle P, Simón-Astudillo I. Memes as Hate Speech: Violence, Humour and Criticism Surrounding the image of Irene Montero. *VISUAL Review International Visual Culture Review / Revista Internacional de Cultura* 2024;16(2):1–16. DOI:10.62161/REVVISUAL.V16.5193
75. Schmid UK, Schulze H, Drexel A. Memes, humor, and the far right’s strategic mainstreaming. *Inf Commun Soc* 2025;28(4):537–56. DOI:10.1080/1369118X.2024.2329610
76. Schmid UK. Humorous hate speech on social media: A mixed-methods investigation of users’ perceptions and processing of hateful memes. *New Media Soc* 2023;27(3):1588–1606. DOI:10.1177/14614448231198169
77. Bouckaert Y, Vofrei L, Jonczyk N, Mertens A, Soliman M, Venz L, et al. Is the joke on you? The impact of sexist humour and gender dynamics on interpersonal work outcomes. *European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology* 2025;34(1):144–59. DOI:10.1080/1359432X.2024.2429850
78. Castellví-Lloveras M. ‘Just Kidding... Or Not?’: Ambiguity, Failure, and Humour in the Representation of Influencers’ Successful Feminity on TikTok. *Medialni Studia* 2023;17(2):107–24.
79. Cowman K. ‘Doing Something Silly’: The Uses of Humour by the Women’s Social and Political Union, 1903–1914. *Int Rev Soc Hist* 2007;52(S15):259–74. DOI:10.1017/S0020859007003239
80. Figueux M, Van Gorp B. Cartoons as bridge builders: dialoguing on radicalization with the ‘suspect community’. *Commun Cult Crit* 2022;15(4):507–19. DOI:10.1093/ccc/tcac024
81. De Ridder A, Vandebosch H, Dhoest A. Examining the hedonic and eudaimonic entertainment experiences of the combination of stand-up comedy and human-interest. *Poetics* 2022;90:101601. DOI:10.1016/j.poetic.2021.101601
82. del Puy Ciriza M. Basque natives vs. Basque learners: The construction of the Basque speaker through satire. *Discourse, Context and Media* 2012;1(4):173–82. DOI:10.1016/J.DCM.2012.06.002
83. Cornips L, De Rooij V. Belonging through Language: Cultural Practices in the Periphery. *Anthropological Journal of European Cultures* 2015;24(1):83–101. DOI:10.3167/ajec.2015.240106
84. Godioli A, Young J. Humor and Free Speech: A Comparative Analysis of Global Case Law. 2023. DOI:10.5281/zenodo.8105760

85. Godioli A, Young J, Fiori BM. Laughing Matters: Humor, Free Speech and Hate Speech at the European Court of Human Rights. *Int J Semiot Law* 2022;35(6):2241–65. DOI:10.1007/s11196-022-09949-8
86. Bogerts L, Fielitz M. ‘Do You Want Meme War?’ Understanding the Visual Memes of the German Far Right. In: Fielitz M, Thurston N, editors. *Online Actions and Offline Consequences in Europe and the US*. transcript Verlag; 2019. page 137–54. DOI:10.1515/9783839446706-010
87. Ebner J. Counter-Creativity. Innovative Ways to Counter Far-Right Communication Tactics. In: Fielitz M, Thurston N, editors. *Post-Digital Cultures of the Far Right*. Bielefeld: transcript Verlag; 2019. page 169–82. DOI:10.14361/9783839446706-012
88. Letourneau NR, Robey DJ, Lamont M. Lights, Camera, Activism: Recognition Strategies in Hollywood and Comedy. *Work Occup* 2025. DOI:10.1177/07308884251336699
89. Ruiz-Gurillo L, Linares-Bernabéu E. Subversive humor in Spanish stand-up comedy. *Humor* 2020;33(1):29–54. DOI:10.1515/HUMOR-2018-0134
90. Mann A. Etnické stereotypy ako zdroje vtipov o Rómoch. In: Podolinská T, Hrustič T, editors. *Čierno-biele svety / Rómovia v majoritnej spoločnosti na Slovensku*. Bratislava: Veda, SAV - Slovenská akadémia vied - Ústav etnológie a sociálnej antropológie Slovenskej akadémie vied; 2015. page 438–79.
91. Borum Chattoo C, Feldman L. *A comedian and an activist walk into a bar: The serious role of comedy in social justice*. Oakland: University of California Press; 2020.
92. Nevado I, Fernández-Ramírez L. El Intermedio. An innovative approach to current affairs satires. *Estudios Sobre el Mensaje Periodístico* 2024;30(4):753–64. DOI:10.5209/EMP.98230
93. Nicolaï JN, Maesele N. Catchier Than COVID: An Analysis of Pandemic Coverage by Dutch News Satire Show Zondag Met Lubach. *International Journal of Communication* 2023;17:6010–6031.
94. Nicolaï J, Maesele P. Satire Between the Lines: Negotiating Genre Hybridity in the Satirical Newsroom of De Ideale Wereld. *Journalism Practice* 2024. DOI:10.1080/17512786.2024.2418928
95. Nicolaï J, Maesele P, Boukes M. The ‘Humoralist’ as Journalistic Jammer: Zondag met Lubach and the Discursive Construction of Investigative Comedy. *Journal Stud* 2022;23(16):2057–77. DOI:10.1080/1461670X.2022.2138948
96. Boukes M. Agenda-Setting With Satire: How Political Satire Increased TTIP’s Saliency on the Public, Media, and Political Agenda. *Polit Commun* 2019;36(3):426–51. DOI:10.1080/10584609.2018.1498816
97. Hardy BW, Gottfried JA, Winneg KM, Jamieson KH. Stephen Colbert’s Civics Lesson: How Colbert Super PAC Taught Viewers About Campaign Finance. *Mass Commun Soc* 2014;17(3):329–53. DOI:10.1080/15205436.2014.891138
98. Brezina M, Dubóczy P, Kandrik M, Krátka Špalková V, Kriššák T. *Communicating Defence in Slovakia and the Czech Republic : Mapping Actors and Narratives online*. Riga: NATO Strategic Communications Centre of Excellence; 2022.
99. Nabi RL, Moyer-Gusé E, Byrne S. All Joking Aside: A Serious Investigation into the Persuasive Effect of Funny Social Issue Messages. *Commun Monogr* 2007;74(1):29–54. DOI:10.1080/03637750701196896

100. Davis LS, León B, Bourk MJ, Zhu L, Finkler W. Infotainment May Increase Engagement with Science but It Can Decrease Perceptions of Seriousness. *Sustainability* 2022;14(17). DOI:10.3390/SU141710659
101. Holm N. The limits of satire, or the reification of cultural politics. *Thesis Eleven* 2023;174(1):81-97. DOI:10.1177/07255136231154266
102. Greenberg J. *The Cambridge Introduction to Satire*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press; 2018. DOI:10.1017/9781139343251
103. Holbert RL, Hmielowski J, Jain P, Lather J, Morey A. Adding Nuance to the Study of Political Humor Effects: Experimental Research on Juvenalian Satire Versus Horatian Satire. *American Behavioral Scientist* 2011;55(3):187-211. DOI:10.1177/0002764210392156
104. Young DG. Theories and Effects of Political Humor: Discounting Cues, Gateways, and the Impact of Incongruities. In: Kenski K, Jamieson KH, editors. *The Oxford Handbook of Political Communication*. Oxford University Press; 2014. page 871-84. DOI:10.1093/oxfordhb/9780199793471.013.29_update_001
105. Ferré-Pavia C, Sintés M, Gayà C. The perceived effects of televised political satire among viewers and the communication directors of political parties: A European case. *European Journal of Cultural Studies* 2016;19(4):299-317. DOI:10.1177/1367549415592892
106. Prior M. *Hooked: How Politics Captures People's Interest*. Cambridge University Press; 2018.
107. Baum MA. Soft News and Political Knowledge: Evidence of Absence or Absence of Evidence? *Polit Commun* 2003;20(2):173-90. DOI:10.1080/10584600390211181
108. Boukes M, Hameleers M. Shattering Populists' Rhetoric with Satire at Elections Times: The Effect of Humorously Holding Populists Accountable for Their Lack of Solutions. *Journal of Communication* 2020;70(4):574-97. DOI:10.1093/joc/jqaa020
109. Monti C, Aiello LM, De Francisci Morales G, Bonchi F. The language of opinion change on social media under the lens of communicative action. *Sci Rep* 2022;12(1):1-11. DOI:10.1038/s41598-022-21720-4
110. Boukes M, LaMarre HL. Satire without borders: the age-moderated effect of one-sided versus two-sided satire on hedonic experiences and patriotism. *Humor - International Journal of Humor Research* 2023;36(1):1-24. DOI:10.1515/humor-2022-0047
111. Mercier H. *Not born yesterday: The science of who we trust and what we believe*. Princeton: Princeton University Press; 2022.
112. LaMarre HL, Landreville KD, Young D, Gilkerson N. Humor Works in Funny Ways: Examining Satirical Tone as a Key Determinant in Political Humor Message Processing. *Mass Commun Soc* 2014;17(3):400-23. DOI:10.1080/15205436.2014.891137
113. Walter N, Cody MJ, Xu LZ, Murphy ST. A Priest, a Rabbi, and a Minister Walk into a Bar: A Meta-Analysis of Humor Effects on Persuasion. *Hum Commun Res* 2018;44(4):343-73. DOI:10.1093/hcr/hqy005
114. Sonnett J. Priming and Framing: dimensions of communication and cognition. In: Brekhus WH, Ignatow G, editors. *The Oxford Handbook of Cognitive Sociology*. Oxford: Oxford University Press; 2019. page 226-40. DOI:10.1093/OXFORDHB/9780190273385.013.13

115. Landreville KD, Holbert RL, LaMarre HL. The Influence of Late-Night TV Comedy Viewing on Political Talk: A Moderated-Mediation Model. *Int J Press Polit* 2010;15(4):482–98. DOI:10.1177/1940161210371506
116. Berman S. The Causes of Populism in the West. *Annual Review of Political Science* 2021;24:71–88. DOI:10.1146/annurev-polisci-041719-102503
117. Sunstein CR. The Law of Group Polarization. *Journal of Political Philosophy* 2002;10(2):175–95. DOI:10.1111/1467-9760.00148
118. Riquelme AR, Carretero-Dios H, Megías JL, Romero-Sánchez M. Joking for Gender Equality: Subversive Humor Against Sexism Motivates Collective Action in Men and Women with Weaker Feminist Identity. *Sex Roles* 2021;84(1–2):1–13. DOI:10.1007/s11199-020-01154-w
119. Vizcaíno-Cuenca R, Riquelme AR, Romero-Sánchez M, Megías JL, et al. Exposure to Feminist Humor and the Proclivity to Collective Action for Gender Equality: The Role of Message Format and Feminist Identification. *Sex Roles* 2023;90:186–201. DOI:10.1007/s11199-023-01430-5
120. Schemer C, Stanyer J, Meltzer CE, Gehle L, Van Aelst P, Theocharis Y, et al. The Relationship between Political Entertainment Media Use and Political Efficacy: A Comparative Study in 18 Countries. *Int J Public Opin Res* 2024;36(4). DOI:10.1093/IJPOR/EDAE046
121. Bennett WL, Segerberg A. The Logic of Connective Action. *Inf Commun Soc* 2012;15(5):739–68. DOI:10.1080/1369118X.2012.670661
122. Chlebcová Hečková A, Veselý M. New forms of the political show in online media and social networks. In: Solik M, Rybansky R, editors. *Megatrends and Media: Reality and Media Bubbles*. Smolenice: Faculty of Mass Media Communication, University of Ss. Cyril and Methodius in Trnava; 2018. page 31–47.
123. Barragán-Romero AI, Caro-Castaño L, Bellido-Pérez E. The appropriation of the meme by the parties: fandom and propaganda in Spanish 2023 general elections. *Revista Latina de Comunicación Social* 2025;2025(83). DOI:10.4185/RLCS-2025-2304
124. Moreno del Río C. El “Zejas” y la “niña de Rajoy”. Análisis sobre el papel del humor en las elecciones generales españolas de 2008. *Revista española de ciencia política* 2010;(22):71–95.
125. Gonawela A, Pal J, Thawani U, van der Vlugt E, Out W, Chandra P. Speaking their Mind: Populist Style and Antagonistic Messaging in the Tweets of Donald Trump, Narendra Modi, Nigel Farage, and Geert Wilders. *Computer Supported Cooperative Work (CSCW)* 2018;27(3–6):293–326. DOI:10.1007/s10606-018-9316-2
126. Sandberg L, Jacobs K, Spierings N. Populist MPs on Facebook: Adoption and emotional reactions in Austria, the Netherlands, and Sweden. *Scan Polit Stud* 2022;45(4):504–28. DOI:10.1111/1467-9477.12239
127. Teune S. Humour as a Guerrilla Tactic: The West German Student Movement’s Mockery of the Establishment. *Int Rev Soc Hist* 2007;52(S15):115–32. DOI:10.1017/S002085900700315X
128. Sierra Infante S. Humor y crítica social en la red en el entorno del 15M. *Discurso & Sociedad* 2012;6(3):611–35.
129. Márquez López M. Wombastic, la batalla gráfica por la reapropiación del cuerpo femenino frente a la amenaza antiabortista de Gallardón. *Teknokultura: Revista de Cultura Digital y Movimientos Sociales* 2018;15(2):275–84. DOI:10.5209/TEKN.59568

130. Simancas-González E, García-López M, Arévalo-Salinas ÁI, Bustos-Díaz J. Online Citizen Activism More than Ten Years After 15M: The Case of “Vote, Please.” *Index.comunicacion* 2023;13(2):225–43. DOI:10.33732/IXC/13/02ACTIVI
131. Buse P, Toribio NT. Ocho apellidos vascos and the Comedy of Minor Differences. *Romance Quarterly* 2015;62(4):229–41. DOI:10.1080/08831157.2015.1068637
132. Marañón IB, Viadero Carral G. El fin de ETA y Ocho apellidos vascos (2013), de Emilio Martínez Lázaro. *Aportes* 2017;94(2):243–69.
133. Eiroa M. The humour factor: Social media reactions to Franco’s exhumation from the Valley of the Fallen. *European Journal of Humour Research* 2022;10(3):54–77. DOI:10.7592/EJHR2022.10.3.652
134. Johann M. Political participation in transition: Internet memes as a form of political expression in social media. *Studies in Communication Sciences* 2022;22(1):149–64. DOI:10.24434/j.scoms.2022.01.3005
135. Šipöczová E. Internet Memes as Part of Political Communication and Participation on the Example of the Slovak Platform Zomri. *Български фолклор* 2023;49(1):038–53.
136. Vicenová R, Trottier D. ‘The first combat meme brigade of the Slovak internet’: hybridization of civic engagement through digital media trolling. *The Communication Review* 2020;23(2):145–71. DOI:10.1080/10714421.2020.1797435
137. Breemen K, Breemen V. Imagining interdisciplinary dialogue in the European Court of Justice’s Deckmyn decision: Conceptual challenges when law and technology regulate parody. *Humor - International Journal of Humor Research* 2022;35(3):447–82. DOI:10.1515/humor-2021-0119
138. Nicolaï J, Maesele P. Stand-up in the age of outrage: how comedians negotiate the repoliticisation of humour. *European Journal of Humour Research* 2024;12(12):56–72. DOI:10.7592/EJHR.2024.12.1.826
139. Moreno C. Efectos de la sátira política a través de programas de infoentretenimiento televisivo en España. ¿Es humor solo para reír o hay algo más en juego? *Papeles del CEIC* 2022;272.
140. Bohman James. *Public deliberation: Pluralism, complexity, and democracy*. Cambridge: MIT Press; 2000.
141. Fraser N. Rethinking the Public Sphere: A Contribution to the Critique of Actually Existing Democracy. *Social Text* 1990;(25/26):56–80. DOI:10.2307/466240
142. Kuipers G. The politics of humour in the public sphere: Cartoons, power and modernity in the first transnational humour scandal. *European Journal of Cultural Studies* 2011;14(1):63–80. DOI:10.1177/1367549410370072
143. Pecourt J, Resina J. Discursive transgressions and security culture: Political-moral panics in the Spanish public sphere. *Papers* 2021;106(1):5–30. DOI:10.5565/REV/PAPERS.2795
144. Barvosa E. *Deliberative Democracy Now: LGBT Equality and the Emergence of Large-Scale Deliberative Systems*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press; 2018.
145. Tsakona V, Popa DE, editors. *Studies in Political Humour: In between political critique and public entertainment*. Amsterdam: John Benjamins; 2011.

146. McHangama J, Alkiviadou N. Hate Speech and the European Court of Human Rights: Whatever Happened to the Right to Offend, Shock or Disturb? *Human Rights Law Review* 2021;21(4):1008–42. DOI:10.1093/hrlr/ngabo15
147. Hendrickx J. ‘Normal news is boring’: How young adults encounter and experience news on Instagram and TikTok. *New Media Soc* 2024. DOI:10.1177/14614448241255955
148. Cauberghe V, Van Wesenbeeck I, De Jans S, Hudders L, Ponnet K. How Adolescents Use Social Media to Cope with Feelings of Loneliness and Anxiety During COVID-19 Lockdown. *Cyberpsychol Behav Soc Netw* 2021;24(4):250–7. DOI:10.1089/cyber.2020.0478
149. Rúas Araújo J, Rodríguez-Martelo T, Fontenla-Pedreira J. La difusión de memes de contenido político durante la tercera ola de la Covid19. *Cultura, Lenguaje y Representacion* 2021;26:209–27. DOI:10.6035/CLR.5843
150. Voolaid P. Representing distance learning in the memes of the first wave of the COVID-19 pandemic: Internet humour as a way of coping and self-defence. *Maetagused* 2021;81:19–44. DOI:10.7592/MT2021.81.voolaid
151. Troitskii S, Castañar G, Laineste L, Fiadotava A. „Putler kaputt “: ajaloomemid Vene sõja kohta Ukrainas. *Methis Studia humaniora Estonica* 2024;26(33):174–97. DOI:10.7592/methis.v26i33.24138
152. Karatzogianni A, Miazhevich G, Denisova A. A Comparative Cyberconflict Analysis of Digital Activism Across Post-Soviet Countries. *Comparative Sociology* 2017;16(1):102–26. DOI:10.1163/15691330-12341415
153. Navarro-Carrillo G, Torres-Marín J, Carretero-Dios H. Do trolls just want to have fun? Assessing the role of humor-related traits in online trolling behavior. *Comput Human Behav* 2021;114:106551. DOI:10.1016/J.CHB.2020.106551
154. Laineste L, Fiadotava A, Šipöczová E, Rubio GC. The cute and the fluffy: pets, humour and personalisation in political communication. *European Journal of Humour Research* 2022;10(4):99–129. DOI:10.7592/EJHR.2022.10.4.692
155. Malavé NM, Slimovich A. Politics and Humour on Twitter/X: Comparing Memes About the Electoral Debates in Argentina and Spain (2019). *Kamchatka* 2023;(22):647–84. DOI:10.7203/KAM.22.25758
156. Villar-Hernández P. The pseudo-political discourse of the second screen. #eldebateentv seen through its prosumers. *Revista Latina de Comunicacion Social* 2020;2020(76):121–41. DOI:10.4185/RLCS-2020-1440
157. Jacobs RN, Smith P. Romance, Irony, and Solidarity. *Sociol Theory* 1997;15(1):60–80. DOI:10.1111/0735-2751.00023
158. Forchtner B, Engelken-Jorge M, Eder K. Towards a revised theory of collective learning processes: Argumentation, narrative and the making of the social bond. *European Journal of Social Theory* 2020;23(2):200–18. DOI:10.1177/1368431018814348
159. Hermes J, Kopitz L. ‘We can sh*t for another 10 years.’ Toilet paper, pandemic politics and cultural citizenship. *Continuum* 2022;36(2):244–59. DOI:10.1080/10304312.2021.1998373
160. Robbins JW. Countering Russian Disinformation. In: *The Diversity of Russia’s Military Power: Five Perspectives* 2020; page 32–9. Available from: <https://www.jstor.org/stable/pdf/resrep26533.8.pdf>

161. Vallentin RT. Pragmatic functions of humor in Berlin's directive Covid-19 Signs. *Pragmatics and Society* 2023;14(2):236–56. DOI:10.1075/ps.22010.val
162. Harro-Loit H, Juurik M. Kommunikatsioon, meedia ja ajakirjanduse eetika . In: Simm K, editor. *Praktilise eetika käsiraamat: õpik gümnaasiumidele ja kõrgkoolidele*. Tartu: University of Tartu Press; 2023. page 242–62.
163. Grančayová M, Kazharski A. 'The Sloakebab': Anti-Islam Agenda in Slovak Parliamentary Elections and Beyond. *Czech Journal of Political Science* 2020;27(3):259–277–259–277. DOI:10.5817/PC2020-3-259
164. Martín Rojo L. Discursos en guerra: crónicas y humor político en torno a la ocupación de Irak. *Discurso & Sociedad* 2007;1(4):575–603.
165. Cingerová N, Dulebová I. Uštipačnosť' and correctness in Slovak online humour. In: *The Ethics of Humour in Online Slavic Media Communication*. London: Routledge; 2021. page 127–38.
166. Verhulsdonk I, Nai A, Karp JA. Are Political Attacks a Laughing Matter? Three Experiments on Political Humor and the Effectiveness of Negative Campaigning. *Polit Res Q* 2022;75(3):720–37. DOI:10.1177/10659129211023590
167. Tsakona V. Parliamentary punning: Is the Opposition more humorous than the ruling party? *The European Journal of Humour Research* 2013;1(2):101–11. DOI:10.7592/EJHR2013.1.2.tsakonaz
168. Willems G. Van cultureel verantwoorde naar plezante films: de heropleving van populaire comedies in de jaren tachtig en de rol van het Vlaamse filmbeleid. *Volkskunde* 2016;117(2):143–61.
169. Zamora-Martínez P, García-Gil S, Gascón-Vera P. El politainment televisivo en la programación española y su relación con los procesos electorales (2015-2022). *Historia Actual Online* 2024;65(65):83–98. DOI:10.36132/kh96hc80
170. Carretero-Dios H, Ruch W. Humor appreciation and sensation seeking: Invariance of findings across culture and assessment instrument? *Humor - International Journal of Humor Research* 2010;23(4):427–45. DOI:10.1515/HUMR.2010.020
171. Ford R, Jennings W. The Changing Cleavage Politics of Western Europe. *Annual Review of Political Science* 2020;23:295–314. DOI:10.1146/annurev-polisci-052217-104957
172. Norris P, Inglehart R. *Cultural Backlash: Trump, Brexit, and Authoritarian Populism*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press; 2019.
173. Crulli M, Emanuele V. Bringing Rokkan into the twenty-first century: the cleavage structure of Western Europe. *J Eur Public Policy* 2025; DOI:10.1080/13501763.2025.2486080
174. Lancaster CM. Not So Radical After All: Ideological Diversity Among Radical Right Supporters and Its Implications. *Polit Stud* 2020;68(3):600–16. DOI:10.1177/0032321719870468
175. Moreno C, Río D. Can ethnic humour appreciation be influenced by political reasons? A comparative study of the Basque Country and Calalonia. *The European Journal of Humour Research* 2013;1(2):24–42. DOI:10.7592/EJHR2013.1.2.moreno
176. Fielitz M, Ahmed R. It's not funny anymore. Far-right extremists' use of humour. Luxembourg: 2021. Available from: https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/document/download/4df68ddb-9ba1-4e04-a7do-1f64dbf302d8_en?filename=ran_ad-hoc_pap_fre_humor_20210215_en.pdf
177. Paluck EL, Green DP. Prejudice reduction: What works? a review and assessment of research and practice. *Annu Rev Psychol* 2009;60:339–67. DOI:10.1146/annurev.psych.60.110707.163607

178. Ofcom, Revealing Reality. Experiences of engaging with the manosphere. 2025. Available from: <https://www.ofcom.org.uk/siteassets/resources/documents/online-safety/research-statistics-and-data/protecting-children/experiences-of-engaging-with-the-manosphere.pdf?v=398550>
179. Budak C, Nyhan B, Rothschild DM, Thorson E, Watts DJ. Misunderstanding the harms of online misinformation. *Nature* 2024;630(8015):45–53. DOI:10.1038/s41586-024-07417-w
180. Osmundsen M, Bor A, Vahlstrup PB, Bechmann A, Petersen MB. Partisan Polarization Is the Primary Psychological Motivation behind Political Fake News Sharing on Twitter. *American Political Science Review* 2021;115(3):999–1015. DOI:10.1017/S0003055421000290
181. Alkiviadou N. Ain't that funny? A jurisprudential analysis of humour in Europe and the U.S. *The European Journal of Humour Research* 2022;10(1):50–61. DOI:10.7592/EJHR.2022.10.1.649
182. Alkiviadou N. Hate speech on social media networks: towards a regulatory framework? *Information & Communications Technology Law* 2019;28(1):19–35. DOI:10.1080/13600834.2018.1494417
183. Matamoros-Fernández A, Bartolo L, Troynar L. Humour as an online safety issue: Exploring solutions to help platforms better address this form of expression. *Internet Policy Review* 2023;12(1). DOI:10.14763/2023.1.1677
184. Kalla JL, Broockman DE. Reducing Exclusionary Attitudes through Interpersonal Conversation: Evidence from Three Field Experiments. *American Political Science Review* 2020;114(2):410–25. DOI:10.1017/S0003055419000923
185. Broockman D, Kalla J. Durably reducing transphobia: A field experiment on door-to-door canvassing. *Science* 2016;352(6282):220–4. DOI:10.1126/science.aad9713
186. Bowles J, Croke K, Larreguy H, Liu S, Marshall J. Sustaining Exposure to Fact-Checks: Misinformation Discernment, Media Consumption, and Its Political Implications. *American Political Science Review* 2025;1–24. DOI:10.1017/S0003055424001394
187. Saffon MP, Urbinati N. Procedural Democracy, the Bulwark of Equal Liberty. *Polit Theory* 2013;41(3):441–81. DOI:10.1177/0090591713476872
188. Lepoutre M. Narrative Counterspeech. *Polit Stud* 2024;72(2):570–89. DOI:10.1177/00323217221129253
189. Fraser R. How to talk back: hate speech, misinformation, and the limits of salience. *Polit Philos Econ* 2023;22(3):315–35. DOI:10.1177/1470594X231167593
190. Smith RM. Toward Progressive Narratives of American Identity. *Polity* 2020;52(3):370–83. DOI:10.1086/708743